

THE DIFFICULTIES AND STRATEGIES IN DIGITIZING LIBRARY RESOURCES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 9

Pages: 933-962

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3017

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14828861

Manuscript Accepted: 01-22-2025

The Difficulties and Strategies in Digitizing Library Resources

Ruth R. Armilla,* Maria Lorena M. Abangan
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Digitizing library resources unlocks knowledge and breaks down physical barriers, allowing anyone to access the collections anytime, anywhere at the same time for the current and future library users. The purpose of this phenomenological qualitative study was to explore the difficulties and strategies of digitizing library resources of academic libraries in Davao region. Twelve (12) academic librarians were conveniently chosen to participate in the study through Key Informant Interview (KII) and data gathered were analyzed using Colaizzi's thematic analysis. Results revealed that the difficulties included technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization, skills and knowledge gaps in digitization, and preservation concerns. These challenges were addressed by employing strategy such as upgrades the technological infrastructure, training and professional development, and new digital preservation methods. The forms of support that they needed from the administrators to facilitate successful digitization projects were increase financial resource allocation, administrative support for policy development, and expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections. Based on the findings, it is recommended that academic librarians implement a well-defined strategy supported by strong administrative backing, to address and overcome obstacles in the digital realm.

Keywords: *library and information science, digitizing library resources, academic librarians, phenomenology, Philippines*

Introduction

Digitizing library resources offers significant opportunities to modernize access to information, ensuring that knowledge becomes more widely available and is preserved for future generations. However, this process is filled with numerous challenges such as technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization, skills and knowledge gaps in digitization, and preservation concerns, that must be addressed to fully realize the potential of digital libraries in enhancing accessibility, preservation, and dissemination of knowledge in the digital age.

Across the globe, most of the academic librarians digitized collections for remote access of information to wider users, but librarians experienced difficulties in digitizing library resources such as data security, funding constraints, and the need for technological infrastructure to secure longevity of digital landscape (Ashikuzzaman, 2023). For example, in Nigeria, academic librarians encounter several challenges that impede effective digitization of their collections. Key obstacles include skills gap and knowledge in digitization, limited funding, and outdated technological infrastructure, where librarians employed strategies like setting planning committee for training and professional development in emerging technologies and implementing new digital preservation methods and acquiring high-end equipment to those obstacles (Nneji, 2018; Udem et al., 2015; Yaya and Adeeko, 2024). Also, Adarkwah et al. (2024) highlighted several challenges faced in Africa, including limited internet access, insufficient technological skills and infrastructure, inadequate funding, and weak digitization policies. To address these issues, strategies were employed which include adopting advanced technologies, developing digital preservation methods, and implementing continuous professional development programs to navigate the digital landscape and improve resource accessibility across the globe. Furthermore, Lefuma (2017) highlighted several threats to accessing digitized collections in Southern Africa, including budget cuts, low internet bandwidth, inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient search skills, shortage of staff, and the absence of collection development policies. To mitigate these challenges, they establish collection development policies, allocate sufficient funding, and hire personnel with the necessary knowledge and skills to ensure an efficient and effective digital landscape.

In New York, academic libraries faced challenges in implementing effective digitization due to limited funds and a lack of dedicated teams. To address these obstacles, they developed new digital preservation methods with the collaboration of the partnering agencies, and invested in advanced technology to ensure the accessibility and reliability of digitized resources (Correia & Luck, 2024; McGinty, 2024). Thus, in digitizing library resources, there is a need for funding, training, and updated technology to advance digital accessibility on a global scale. At the same time, there is a need to secure a digital preservation method, to carefully plan what to digitize and how, and to have teamwork and collaboration to come up with a successful digitization of resources.

Transforming printed materials to digital format has been recognized as a hurdle of academic librarians in the ASEAN context. In India, libraries face issues such as technological obsolescence, inadequate funding, and barriers to information accessibility, both of which impact the availability and reliability of digital resources. To address these issues, ongoing professional development has become essential, enabling library staff to keep pace with rapid technological changes and maintain effective digital practices through securing digital preservation methods (Pandey & Misra, 2014; Soni, 2023). In addition, Kaur (2015) added that digitizing library resources can transform the role of librarians from book providers to e-providers, which raises issues regarding guiding principles or policies for

digitization initiatives. As such, digital preservation methods are key to overcoming these obstacles. In Indonesia, librarians face barriers to digitization, including inadequate facilities and infrastructure, limited digitization skills among librarians, insufficient institutional support from schools or governing bodies, and a lack of funding. To overcome these challenges, libraries often seek additional support for technical upgrades, training programs to build staff competencies, and collaborative partnerships to share resources and expertise (Indah et al., 2024; Nafisah, 2022). In Malaysia, the primary challenges hindering an effective and efficient digital landscape included inadequate facilities and infrastructure, skills and knowledge gaps in digitization, and preservation concerns. To overcome these obstacles, libraries have allocated sufficient budgets to acquire high-quality digitization equipment, implemented comprehensive training programs to enhance the professional skills of personnel, and developed targeted preservation methods to ensure the longevity and accessibility of digital resources (Azim et al., 2018).

Furthermore, at Shri Saraswati Social Work College, converting printed resources into digital formats provides faster access to information. However, implementing digital libraries presents several challenges, including the costs of hardware and software maintenance, IT infrastructure, copyright and intellectual property concerns, and preservation security. Therefore, strategic planning was employed to address these difficulties (Ingle, 2022). Also, in Bangkok, during the work process, the databases team encountered several challenges related to data management due to the lack of guidelines provided by the staff. To address these issues, the staff has decided to develop guidelines for the digital work process (Rungcharoensuksri, 2016).

Thus, common problems in ASEAN countries were observed, highlighting the significant impact of digitizing library resources when following standard preservation strategies, policies, adequate technology, collaboration among colleagues, and sufficient funding for acquiring the hardware and software needed for digitization.

In the national context, digitization is a vital step toward modernizing libraries in the Philippines, ensuring that valuable resources are preserved and made accessible to a broader audience. However, barriers to implementing a digitization program includes limited staff, insufficient physical space, inadequate equipment, and restricted funding, as encountered by the University of Diliman. To address these challenges, digitization initiatives, guidelines, standards, and collaborative consortia for sharing facilities and expertise were employed (Lagas & Isip, 2023). Also, Dela Cruz (2018), added that the University of the Philippines National College of Public Administration and the Governance library encountered lack of digitization policies that impede on digital landscape. Thus, digitization policies and guidelines were recommended to resolve the issues.

Furthermore, National Library of the Philippines digitized library resources for remote access but it faced numerous challenges, including copyright and privacy issues, budget constraints, and a shortage of IT skills in which librarians initiated strategies like digital preservation method to overcome those challenges (Uy, 2023). In addition, digitizing library resources at the La Union library involves challenges such as the lack of guidelines or standard policies, which impede digitization efforts. As such, a digitization manual model was developed to address these challenges (Lacuata, 2020). Also, Benguit State University encountered challenges related to budget allocation and skills gap among personnel. However, they continued to pursue success in the digital landscape by collaborating with partnering agencies and providing training for their staff in the digitization process (Kipaan, n.d.).

Thus, the proper execution of guidelines and standard policies on digitization can help resolve the obstacles. At the same time, having adequate funds, as well as human and technical expertise, is essential to safeguarding the collections from technological threats. In the local context, several of my colleagues in the Davao region have shared their difficulties in digitizing their collections, citing technological and infrastructure barriers, gaps in skills and knowledge, and preservation concerns that hinder successful digitization efforts, where academic librarians often experience a range of emotions, such as frustration, stress, resilience, and even optimism, as they navigate these challenges. Although their mood may fluctuate between stress and optimism, the drive to adapt and innovate keeps them motivated despite the obstacles. They feel a deep sense of responsibility to adopt creative approaches, such as upgrading technological infrastructure, pursuing training and professional development, and developing new digital preservation methods to achieve a successful digitization initiative.

Furthermore, in today's era, the digitization of library resources is essential for all learners, making education more accessible without disruption, regardless of their location or the devices they use. As a mandate stated on Senate Bill No. 477 that all higher education institutions (HEIs) and the Department of Education (DepEd) standards stipulated that digitization of library collections enhances accessibility for learners, ensuring that they can access resources with ease. Requiring the institution to transition their library collection into digital format helps to address issues such as resource management, technology integration and users' engagement. This legislative initiative serves as the foundation for studying the challenges and difficulties in digitization of academic libraries, while they are in the process of digitizing. The present study aims to explore the difficulties and strategies of academic libraries in digitizing library resources. Thus, these reasons as being reflected, led me to conduct this study to give a value-added service to the patrons as well as enhance librarians' knowledge in digitizing library resources. In the end, sharing the findings of this research through publication will contribute to the body of knowledge and potentially enable academic librarians to innovate their strategies in digitizing library collections.

This study was viewed through the lens of Open Archival Information System Reference Model by the Consultative Community for Space Data System (2002), the Digital Curation Lifecycle Model of Higgins (2008), and the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping of Lazarus and Folkman (1984).

The Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model by the Consultative Community for Space Data System (2002) explains the coping techniques and stages in digitizing library resources that remain accessible and usable over time. It helps in managing the entire lifecycle of digital information, from acquisition to dissemination, including storage, access, and preservation that can promote seamless resource sharing and collaboration with other institutions compatible to the standard systems, where librarians organize and manage the digital collections efficiently.

In the context of this study, OAIS served as a guide for academic librarians to minimize the risk management and implement strategies such as systematic process for managing digital assets that are properly categorized, stored, and maintained in a manner that ensures the longevity on it. Thus, this study was beneficial to academic librarians who would like to enhance and develop their learning and capacity as to the proper way of digitizing and preserving resources in an extended period of time.

Moreover, the Digital Curation Lifecycle Model by Higgins (2008) provides a comprehensive framework for managing in digitization process throughout its lifecycle. In the context of the study, this model served as a guide in selecting appropriate resources of which are prioritized for digitization. Once materials are selected, the next step involves the actual digitization process, including scanning physical documents, converting formats, and ensuring high-quality digital files in which the critical process as it lays the foundation for future access and usability of the library's digital collections. The model emphasizes the importance of describing digital resources accurately, which helps users locate and utilize these resources efficiently that librarians must implement standardized metadata inputs to ensure consistency and accessibility of the digitized resources.

In digitizing library resources, it emphasizes the importance of preservation planning, risk assessment, and ongoing maintenance to protect digital assets from degradation, obsolescence, and loss. As such, this theory encourages academic librarians to develop sustainability plans to ensure the continued management, preservation, and accessibility of digitized materials.

Furthermore, this study is anchored on the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping of Lazarus and Folkman (1984). This theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how individuals navigate challenging situations, and this perspective can be applied to the realm of digitization coping strategies. Additionally, this model differentiates coping strategies into two categories: problem-focused and emotion-focused. Problem-focused coping involves identifying specific challenges in the digitization process, such as technical issues or resource constraints, and developing practical solutions to overcome them. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping involves managing the emotional responses elicited by stressful situations that librarians experience, such as feelings of frustration, anxiety, or overwhelm due to the complexity of the digitization process which help to regulate emotions. Individuals appraise a situation as either stressful or not, and their coping strategies are influenced by this appraisal.

The model also emphasizes that the stress-coping process is ongoing and adaptive. In the context of this study, it guides librarians to implement strategies and cope with the hurdles. As libraries digitize more resources, they can continually reassess their strategies based on user feedback and technological advancements. This constant process helps librarians remain responsive to the needs of their users and the challenges of the digital landscape. In fact, successful digitization can enhance resource accessibility, improve user satisfaction, and foster a culture of innovation within the library.

Finally, this study offers valuable insights into how academic librarians can effectively manage stress during the digitization of library resources. By recognizing the stages of appraisal and coping, libraries can implement strategies that do not only address technological challenges but also support their staff and users through the transition to a digital future. In fact, this approach ensures the resilient to changes, challenges, and threats in digitization of resources.

Research Questions

The purpose of this phenomenological qualitative study was to explore the difficulties and strategies of digitizing library resources of academic libraries in Davao region. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the difficulties of academic librarians in digitizing library resources?
2. What are the strategies employed by academic librarians to overcome challenges in digitizing library resources?
3. What forms of support do academic librarians need from the administrators in digitizing library resources?

Methodology

Research Design

This study is qualitative in nature employing the phenomenological approach to delve deeper into the difficulties and strategies of academic librarians in digitizing library resources in Davao region. Phenomenology involves delving into the firsthand experiences of participants, seeking to explore the reasons behind their behavior and understanding how they perceive and interpret their actions (Tenny et al., 2022; Ugwu & Val, 2023). Moreover, phenomenological research is focused on studying participants' lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how they comprehend those experiences and to identify the essence of the phenomenon by interpreting the participants' emotions, perceptions, and beliefs (Ho & Limpaecher, 2022). In the context of the study, the qualitative design using the phenomenological approach was employed in order to explore the difficulties and strategies of academic librarians in digitizing the library resources of academic libraries in Davao region.

Participants

In this study, I interviewed twelve (12) participants that were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria in order to emphasize the scope and limitation of the study. The following inclusion criteria were observed: the participants were licensed academic librarians, working at private higher educational institutions within Davao Region, and have working experience in digitizing the library resources with at least two (2) years in service to secure the accuracy of the gathered data.

On the other hand, excluded in this study were academic librarians working outside Davao Region, librarians that were serving in school, special, and public libraries, as well as paraprofessional library staff who are not practicing digitization initiatives. Moreover, the defined criteria ensured that the study accurately represented the academic librarians' difficulties and strategies of digitizing library resources. This number meet the minimum requirements for achieving data saturation in phenomenological research. Saturated data could be attained at five to twenty-five participants (Creswell, 2018).

This study utilized the convenience sampling technique in determining the participants to be interviewed. Convenience sampling technique is a non-probability technique in determining the participants who have direct involvement or experience with digitization. According to Nikolopoulou, (2023) convenience sampling is a commonly employed method in qualitative research that prioritizes gathering information from participants who are easily accessible to the researcher. It also entails the process of recognizing and choosing individuals in any location who possessed both knowledge and expertise in a topic of interest.

In the context of this study, the convenience sampling technique was employed because I easily selected participants who were near in my location and could be conveniently interviewed in the study. It is the easiest way to interview participants to gather the accurate data particularly those academic librarians who started converting their printed materials into digital format as it is now the trends in the academic libraries in Davao region. I believe the I gained relevant information from the participants' lived experiences in digitizing their library resources.

Instrument

In order to collect the information from the informants of this study, a Key Informant Interview (KII) was employed. These interview questions were taken directly from the interview guide protocol in order to gain detailed information or the points of view from the lived experience of the participants in digitizing library resources (Sturkey, 2013). In this study, interviews were conducted through face-to-face and online platform. I specifically used Google meet video conference for the online interviews due to some librarians' preference. I also conducted a face-to-face interview because of the internet intermittent connection of the participants. Also, I included other resources like articles from journals, and books which are helpful tools to support the data gathered in the study. Turner (2015) stated that a variety of online journal articles and books significantly support the data gathered from the participants points of view. Following the interview, I compiled the participants' responses and emailed the results to them for counterchecking. This allowed me to confirm that their answers throughout the interview were accurate and correct.

Procedure

In the conduct of this study, I followed a set of procedures to effectively collect the data through KII. The ethical considerations were also acknowledged and were followed responsibly. First, before collecting the data, I sent a request letter to the Dean of the Graduate School asking permission to conduct this study. Then, I secured an ethical clearance from Cor Jesu College, Inc. Research Ethics Committee (CJC-REC). In this study, experienced academic librarians were chosen as key informants because of their direct involvement in the digitization of library resources in the libraries in Davao region. An interview guide that was validated by three internal experts was utilized, leading to the main research questions of the study.

Furthermore, I sent a letter requesting the presidents of the different colleges and universities for me to conduct the study through both online and face-to-face interviews. Through these modalities, the participants were able to understand the goal of my research and it also allowed me to understand and explore the study in an in-depth discussion. In addition, I asked the target participants of those private colleges and universities who gave their permission to allow me to perform the interview and collect relevant data. For the academic librarians, I requested them personally through a formal request letter with the attached informed consent that gave them an opportunity to decide to voluntarily participate in the study.

Also, I explained to the participants the nature, scope, and purpose of the research study because it was needed for clarity and awareness among the participants to ensure understanding of the primary reason for the interview. Also, verbal and written consent were given to the participants which served as an indication that they agreed to be part of the study.

In gathering the relevant data, an in-depth interview or key informant interview was used. In conducting the interview, both face-to-face and online modalities were employed depending on the choice of the selected twelve (12) participants. Before the interview, I established rapport to make the participants comfortable and feel at ease. This allowed me to have a free-flowing of ideas and responses to the research questions. In obtaining unlimited responses from the key informants, follow-up questions were raised, encouraging them to share more detailed and necessary information related to the study.

Lastly, all the responses that were gathered during the interview were recorded using an audio tape, cellular phone voice recorder

software application, and note-taking. The data and information were classified to identify the difficulties, strategies employed, and forms of support given to them by the school and other different organizations.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the process of making sense of, interpreting, and conceptualizing data to find general statements among various data sets (Elridge, 2024). Also, it entails reflecting on the data obtained, as well as asking question and making interpretations during the study (Creswell, 2018). The data gathered was analyzed using the method of Colaizzi (1978). It involved the process of examining, analyzing, and conceptualizing data in order to find general statements among different types of data (Hotjar, 2023).

First, I transcribed the participants' responses verbatim and translated it into English and all the narration given by the participants during the interview. In the conduct of this study, I ensured that I conducted the interviews, which helped me gain a holistic sense of the experiences of the participants. I also ensured that all transcripts taken from the audio and video recording were well-consolidated and transcribed for me to understand and come up with the general theme.

Second, by analyzing the research questions and extracting significant statements from the transcriptions, I collated and identified the essential statements through reading and re-reading the transcript, and then identified the significant statements that directly relate to the investigated phenomenon.

Third, to avoid any errors or misinterpretations, the significant statements were given precise and accurate meanings. In the conduct of the study, I extracted and recorded the significant statements on a separate file, and noted the participant's verbatim responses. Likewise, I read the transcript several times and analyzed each one. I wrote the statements separately for each of the participants using codes to ensure anonymity, together with the transcript page and line number.

Fourth, formulated meanings were categorized into common themes, leading to the development of clustered themes and emergent themes after a thorough analysis. I selected responses that were significant to formulate meanings for each identified significant statement that I extracted from the participant's narratives. After that, I formulated the meanings and identified the significant statements addressed by the participants. Likewise, bracketing was applied when necessary to avoid misinterpretation of the participant's views. Then, the formulated meanings were coded and labelled and I gave it to my research adviser for correction and consistency of the meanings.

Also, I assigned themes into clusters and into the group of formulated meanings with similar type. I clustered the formulated meanings into themes related to the common responses. My research adviser checked the accuracy of the clustered themes, and counterchecked the final themes that emerged in the study.

Fifth, the study's findings were interpreted to provide a comprehensive description of the investigated phenomena. In the context of this study, I wrote a comprehensive description of the phenomenon about the study. Also, I combined all the significant statements, formulated meanings, clustered themes and emerging themes into a description to create an overall structure. I presented it to my research adviser to confirm its accuracy and its reflection on the experiences of academic librarians.

Sixth, the underlying structure of the phenomenon was described to ensure a thorough understanding. Lastly, I identified the fundamental structure that revealed by explanation. In the conduct of this study, I synthesized the detailed description to generate the fundamental findings.

Aside from that, I provided a printed copy of the transcribed interview to the participants for verification, specifically the interview guide protocol, and conducted a member checking from the participants to ensure the richness, accuracy, and credibility of the results. Likewise, I properly performed the data collection methods and the data analysis and interpretation to create accurate, truthful, and valid research results. Following these methods and steps helped me develop a sense responsibility as a researcher in this study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards play a paramount role in the conduct of the phenomenological study, particularly due to its intimate nature involving the personal lives of our participants. I prioritized the safeguarding of the participants' identities and sensitive information to prevent any future complications. Ethical considerations in research encompass the protection of human subjects and adherence to socially responsible and acceptable research practices (Bhandari, 2021). As noted by Gupta (2017), various ethical challenges, such as privacy, security, transparency, and confidentiality, can arise during in-depth interviews. Hence, in the context of this study, I rigorously adhered to the following ethical principles: anonymity, confidentiality, and obtaining informed consent from all participants, further ensuring ethical compliance by seeking approval from the school research ethics committee.

Informed Consent. Informed consent involved continuous communication between the researcher and the participants to ensure participants' comfort (Owen, 2010). In addition, participation in any research must be entirely voluntary, free from any form of pressure or coercion (Methodologist, 2023).

In this study, I obtained a written consent from the participants. Informed consent gave them comprehensive information, enabling them to make a voluntary and well-informed decision about their participation. This information encompassed the study's objectives,

procedures, potential risks, discomfort, or adverse effects, potential research benefits, and their right to decline, withdraw, skip questions, or discontinue participation at any time. Also, I did not pressure participants to go beyond their comfort levels or answer questions they were unwilling to address. Adjustments were made if participants felt uncomfortable during the interview. It is important to note that only those who have signed and fully agreed to participate were considered as participants of the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Privacy entails managing the scope, timing, and conditions of sharing one's self with others (UCI Office of Research, 2020). In addition, confidentiality pertains to the researcher's commitment to handle, store, and distribute research data in a manner that prevents any improper disclosure of information gathered from and about research participants (Reno, 2019). This is another significant ethical consideration in this study, as participants may possess sensitive information, they wish to keep private, and revealing it could potentially harm their personal identity (Hassan, 2024).

In the context of the study, aside from obtaining the informed consent from the participants, I also took measures to ensure the confidentiality of their information and protect their privacy by using codes. I refrained from disclosing their names or the institutions they were affiliated with in any reports based on the interview data that was collected. Furthermore, I followed the standard data usage policies that safeguard the anonymity of both the participants and their affiliated institutions when using the information and records I gathered. Participants were informed that the collected data would be used exclusively for research purposes.

Additionally, I conducted the interviews in a private setting, without the presence of faculty or administrators from my institution, and they had no access to the raw notes or transcripts. Prior to the interviews, I addressed any questions the participants about the informed consent to ensure their satisfaction, and I provided them with copies of the informed consent containing all necessary signatures. Lastly, I adhered to The Data Privacy Act of 2012 in protecting individuals' personal information from unauthorized access, ensuring that sensitive data like social security numbers, financial records, and health information were kept safe (Tobin, 2023; National Privacy Commission, 2023). In this study, participant rights to privacy and confidentiality were taken into consideration. Data privacy is a crucial fundamental human right whose realization is directly impacted by the gathering, storage, use, and disclosure of personal data (Price, 2020; Gomez et al., 2023). To guarantee the privacy and confidentiality of this study, I informed the selected participants beforehand that their answers were also be handled thoroughly and would not be posted in public domains nor shared with my colleagues.

With regards to the recorded audio, video, and notes transcription of the interview, the files were kept for collection of information purposes only and will be disposed permanently after two (2) years. Rest assured that the recorded, audio and video, notes transcription will be kept privately and confidentiality will be followed strictly.

Anonymity. Anonymity refers to the condition in which the researchers do not have knowledge of the individual subjects' identities (Hassan, 2024). In this study, the anonymity of the participants was strictly observed and protected. The actual names of the participants were kept confidential and were replaced with codes in order to protect their true identities. Also, I substituted their real names with identifiers such as KIIa and assigned numbers from one to fifteen. It is very essential not only to provide the participants' names but also to safeguard them against any potential discrimination or harm. As a result, the true identities of the participants in this study remained undisclosed to ensure their safety and privacy. Indeed, in protecting their privacy, I gave them the freedom not to attach their real names, instead use codes for the duration of the interview which was recorded. I assured the participants that there were no other people who have access to the data gathered.

Risk, Benefits and Conflict of Interest. This study holds value for the participants as it provided them with a platform to express their challenges in digitizing library resources. Also, I gave them an opportunity to voice their concerns to school administrators, various associations particularly in the field of librarianship organizations, as well as the new generations and middle-aged librarians. Moreover, participants shared their diverse coping strategies for addressing their various circumstances. Consequently, their experiences served as a source of inspiration for fellow librarians who practice and establish digitization of library resources.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the experiences of academic librarians in digitizing library resources. To answer the research questions, the result was divided into three parts: the difficulties of academic librarians in digitizing library resources, strategies of academic librarians to overcome their difficulties in digitizing library resources, and the form of support academic librarians need from the administration in order to overcome their difficulties in digitizing library resources. A discussion on the obtained results in each research question was also provided.

Difficulties of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources

In the context of academic libraries, difficulties refer to the challenges, or risks that have been encountered by academic librarians in converting physical collections (books, documents, etc) into digital format, where Academic librarians often experience a range of emotions, such as frustration, stress, resilience, and even optimism, as they navigate these challenges. Thus, this study asked about the difficulties encountered in digitizing library collections, and three (3) themes emerged, namely; technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization, skills and knowledge gaps in digitization, and preservation concerns.

Table 1. *Thematic Map on the Difficulties of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources*

Difficulties of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources
<p>FIRST THEME</p> <p>Technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization</p> <p>Difficulty in digitizing resources due to unavailable equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires specialized and high-end digitized equipment • Having difficulty in oversized resources that is not suitable to the available scanner <p>Need of Software in digitizing resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs software enhancement for the quality control measures of contents • Maintain high-quality control in digitizing resources thru suitable application <p>Insufficient budget</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have difficulty in the budget in conducting digitization initiatives • Budget constraints to acquire technological structure in preservation • Difficulty in sustaining long-term financial support for continuous updates and preservation efforts <p>Inadequate internet connectivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited wifi facilities • Frequent internet connection interruption • Inaccessible content due to domain name
<p>SECOND THEME</p> <p>Skills and knowledge gaps in digitization</p> <p>Need new skills on the adaptation of digitization technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs training for skills enhancement on digitization • Technological enhancement and active engagement to digital trends • Need to explore and more capacity building on Dspace system due to its marc tags <p>Lack of knowledge for digitization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need in-depth knowledge in utilizing technology • Having difficulty for scanning
<p>THIRD THEME</p> <p>Preservation Concerns</p> <p>Lack of data security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient file back-up • Data losses <p>Lack of preservation policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires adequate procedures to guarantee long-term preservation • Needs enhancement on the digitization policy <p>Insufficient file format</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor scanning quality • Need to use a high-resolution equipment and proper scanning techniques • Needs enhancement on metadata inputs

Technological and Infrastructure Barriers in Digitization. This refers to the various challenges that academic librarians face, namely: difficulty in digitizing resources due to unavailable equipment, need of software in digitizing resources, insufficient budget, and inadequate internet connectivity.

One common instance among librarians is the required specialized and high-end digitized equipment. Maam Lin shared that

“The difficulties sa pagdigitized ng collection is budget, equipment, and time siguro, ang pag scan lang medyo lisod lang siya, kay cam scanner lang akong gigamit sa cellphone lang maam.” (Transcript 8, Page 14, line 1-5)

(The difficulties in digitizing collections are budget, equipment, and time, maybe the scanning is quite difficult because I am just using cam scanning on my cellphone, ma’am.)

Another participant shared her thoughts on the challenges faced when specialized equipment for digitization is unavailable and it needs to require specialized and high-end digitized equipment for securing the quality control measures of the content.

“We have also other large resources na needed talaga ng high-end equipment, yon yong parang challenge sa amin na part, kasi kailangan mong e please or encourage the admin to acquire those” (Maam Ga, transcript 9, Page 16-17, Line 25-29)

(We have also other large resources that really need high-end equipment that is a challenge for us, because we need to encourage or persuade the administration to acquire those.)

The same scenario was encountered by Maam Le in digitizing library resources. It was quite challenging on her part without the use of high-end equipment, as she shared that

“Requires the use of specialized equipment and software” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 19, Line 4)

In connection, there is also a concern on having difficulty in oversized resources that is not suitable to the available scanner. Sir Cio shared his experienced as shown below.

“The difficulty is with oversized books and resources that may not fit onto the cradle of the digital scanner, as they extend beyond the scope of the camera and scanner whether V-shaped, or flatbed; 3-dimensional objects, artifacts and realia are also difficult to scan if you only have V-shaped or flatbed” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 1-5)

(I have difficulty with oversized books and resources that do not fit onto the cradle of a digital scanner, as they extend beyond the range of the camera and scanner, whether V-shaped or flatbed. Additionally, 3-dimensional objects, artifacts, and realia are challenging to scan with only V-shaped or flatbed scanners.)

Based from the participants' statements, technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization can significantly hinder on digitization efforts because not all resources will convert into digital format like the large-scale resources due to unavailability of specialized equipment. In fact, librarians can only digitize a fraction of their collections, often prioritizing materials compatible with their existing equipment.

Another common instance among librarians is the need of software in digitizing resources, where Maam Fe shared her thoughts on the lack of software enhancement for the quality control measures of contents.

"Problems with hardware or software, compatibility issues, security vulnerabilities" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 12, Line 42-47)

(I have problems with hardware or software, compatibility issues, and security vulnerabilities.)

It is also attested by participant 6, who experienced digitizing library resources. Her concern is the lack of software enhancement to secure the quality control measures of the content.

"The difficulties, first sa software to used sa pagdigitized need nimo og technology, aside from software naa pod tay hardware which is atong scanner, since from printed to digital na siya. Ikaduha unsa na mga software ang gamiton para ma enhanced ang quality sa image. Sa pagconvert maam from image to pdf, naa pod me ginagamit na software na scan taylor kinahanglan pa nimo siya eh explore kay open-source man siya dili siya updated from time to time" (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 21-23, Line 1-7, 20-22)

(I have difficulties on the software to be used for digitization since it needs technology. Aside from software, we also have hardware, which is the scanner, since it converts printed materials into digital format. Second, the software used to enhance the quality of the image. In converting, from image to PDF, we also use software called Scan Taylor, but I still need to explore it because it is open-source and is not updated regularly.)

Aside from lack of software enhancement, there is also difficulty in maintaining high-quality control in digitizing resources thru suitable application, where participant 3 shared her experienced, to wit;

"Pinakamahirap doon is yong nakabind na siya, sometimes yong pinaka edge ng newspaper hindi na naming makita, so we opted to cut nalang yong tinali naming para makita ang content ng newspaper" (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 6, Line 69-81)

(The most difficult part is when it is already bound, sometimes the newspaper edge content can no longer see, so we opt to cut the binding to access the content of the newspaper.)

As participant 6 shared also her thought about the enhancement of the quality content, to wit;

"Maintain high-quality digital reproductions that are faithful to the original materials" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 11, Line 25-27)

(I need to maintain high-quality reproductions that look like an original one)

Lastly, participant 8 shared also her thought, as she mentioned that;

"The potential risk is hago siya kay blurry ang pagka picture so need siya magpicture og balik" (Maam Lin, Transcript 8, Page 15, Line 14-15)

(The potential risk is that the picture may be blurry, so it needs to be retaken.)

Academic librarians face challenges in maintaining high-quality control of digitized resources due to unsuitable applications and software. Therefore, further exploration of applications that can enhance the quality of content to resemble the original is necessary. While some librarians have software for quality control, it may require expert modification. Additionally, there are free applications that are easy to modify, but these may not be sustainable for long-term use; over time, software can become outdated, potentially making digitized resources inaccessible.

Another dilemma encountered by librarians was the insufficient budget, which impedes the successful execution of digitization initiatives. In consonance to this, Maam My shared her statement about the difficulty in the budget in conducting digitization initiatives.

"Pinakadifficult lang sa akin is yong funding, kasi pagsabi nating digitization it requires huge amount of budget" (Maam My, Transcript 5, Page 9, Line 1-12)

(The most challenging for me is the funding because digitization requires budget.)

Participant 9 shared her thoughts that budget constraints in acquiring the technological infrastructure for preservation greatly affect digitization initiatives. Ma'am Ga mentioned that

"One of the difficulties na na-experienced namin is the budget constraints. Kasi when you digitized there are also some large resources

na hindi lang siya kaya ng simpleng scanner, dapat meron siyang budget na allocated to acquire a high-end equipment for scanner” (Maam Ga, Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 1-5)

(One of the difficulties we experienced is budget constraints. When you digitize, there are also some large resources that cannot be handled by a simple scanner; there needs to be an allocated budget to acquire high-end scanning equipment.)

Sir Gar also experienced difficulties with digitization due to budget constraints in acquiring technological infrastructure. He shared that:

“Some difficulties encountered in digitizing library resources are the availability of the equipment, funds.” (Sir Gar, Transcript 7, Page 13, Line 1-2)

(The difficulties I have experienced was the lack of skills development training of the personnel on digitization efforts.)

In this regard, academic librarians are having difficulty sustaining long-term financial support for continuous updates and preservation efforts due to the lack of standardized policies. Ma'am Fe shared her experience stating that,

“Digitizing library resources involves numerous challenges for academic librarians. One is the technological infrastructure which lack of advanced hardware and software for scanning, digitizing, and storing digital materials. More IT support is needed to maintain digital systems and manage digital archives” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 10, Line 1-6)

(Digitizing library resources involves numerous challenges for academic librarians. One is the technological infrastructure, which includes a lack of advanced hardware and software for scanning, digitizing, and storing digital materials. More IT support is needed to maintain digital systems and manage digital archives.)

Based on the participants' point of view, the difficulty in digitizing library resources is often escalated by the unavailability of necessary equipment and insufficient budgets. Libraries face challenges in acquiring the technological structure in preservation due to budget constraints. As a result, libraries struggle to meet the growing demand for digital access to resources, hindering their ability to preserve and share valuable materials with users.

On the other hand, inadequate internet connectivity was one of the difficult factors that can affect the accessibility and usability of the digitized resources, particularly the limited WiFi facilities. Maam Lin shared her thought about this.

“Dili stable ang among internet connection, tapos naa pod ubang computer dili moandar problema jud siya maam” (Maam Lin, Transcript 8, Page 1, Line 10-13)

(Our internet connection is not stable, and some computers will not work, which is really a problem.)

The same scenario was encountered by Maam Zel stating that the digitized collections cannot be accessed easily due to the limited WiFi facilities.

“Wala me internet connection sa library we are depending our institution's internet” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 7-12)

(I don't have internet connection in the library; we are relying on our institution's internet)

Pertaining to the clustered theme above, a problem will really occur on the digitization efforts if there is a frequent internet connection interruption, which leads to inaccessibility of the digitized collections. Maam Zel shared on this:

“The difficulties in digitizing library resources were internet access and financial cause” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 1-2)

(The difficulties in digitizing library resources were internet access and financial constraints.)

Another factor that can hinder in accessing the digitized resources was the inaccessible content due to domain name. Maam Zel shared her thought on this.

“The potential risk that I mention earlier is our internet connectivity, because there is a changes in our internet sa business provider, so our services also will be hampered at the moment” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 13-20)

(The potential risk I mentioned earlier is our internet connectivity, because there are changes with our internet service provider, our services will also be hampered at the moment)

Maam Ghie also mentioned that she encountered dilemma in the domain name of the digitized resources.

“I think yong pag online sometimes hindi siya ma access, yon siguro siya ang risk doon sa digitized library. Kasi halimbawa sa online database kasi as you observed when you do your research, sometimes meron talagang mga title na pagclick wala talagang labas na content kasi mali yong domain name” (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 3, Line 51-58)

(I think the issue with online access is that sometimes it is not accessible. That could be the risk with a digitized library. For example, in an online database, as you have observed when doing research, sometimes there are titles that, when clicked, do not display any

content because the domain name is incorrect.)

As dilemma arised in digitization efforts, inadequate internet connectivity can severely impact digitization initiatives in libraries and other institutions, particularly through limited Wi-Fi facilities, frequent connection interruptions, and inaccessible content due to domain name issues, because it can limit the number of devices that can connect to the network at once, and affect users in searching unlimited digitized resosources. Without reliable internet connectivity, digitization initiatives face significant obstacles in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and usability. For successful digitization, consistent, high-speed, and well-managed internet infrastructure is essential.

Skills and Knowledge Gaps in Digitization. The librarian's lack of knowledge and the necessary skills for digitizing library resources can lead to poor-quality, compromised digital library with accuracy issues, inefficiencies, and potential damage to valuable resources. The results can be far from ideal. One of the persisting difficulties of academic librarians were the need of new skills on the adaptation of digitization technology, and lack of knowledge for digitization.

Another difficulty encountered by academic librarians when it comes to the need of new skills on the adaptation of digitization initiatives was the needs training for skills enhancement on digitization to secure the proper procedure and execution in digitization efforts. Sir Cio shared his thoughts on this.

"In other words, if not just the technology or digitized resources that you are going to worry about, but you need to study the entire system, which you have installed prior to the digitalization." (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 15-22)

(In other words, it is not just the technology or digitized resources that I need to worry about, but I also need to study the entire system that I have installed prior to the digitization.)

Participant 4 also shared his experience regarding the difficulties of digitization initiatives, particularly concerning the personnel who require training to enhance their skills for the proper execution of digitization efforts.

"The staff expertise training in digitizing library resources, kung ano ba yong unahing eh prioritize na collection, and also yong metadata sa cataloging kung pano natin eh classify sa Dspace system, kung paano natin eh transcribe" (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 1-6)

(There is a need of staff expertise training in digitizing library resources to know which collections should be prioritized, and also the metadata in cataloging, including how we classify it in the DSpace system and how we transcribe it.)

Other challenges faced by academic librarians in digitizing library resources was the technological enhancement and active engagement to digital trends, as attested by Sir Cio.

"The work environment now is more on the virtual world, because if you'd notice our students are into mobile applications. So, this is a challenge that all of us librarians should be aware of" (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 3, Line 49-54)

(I need to enhance my skills on technology because we are now in the digital era and users are reliant on it, especially in retrieving the information.)

The same dilemma was encountered by the participant 6 stating that technological enhancement trends on digitization will affect the execution of the digitized collections, since technology was evolved.

"Requiring them to adapt to new technologies, develop new skills, and balance traditional and emerging duties" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page1, Line 34-39)

(I need to develop my skills on digitization initiatives by embracing the new trends of technology for easy access and retrieval of information.)

Maam Zel also shared her thoughts on the difficulties encountered, when there is no engagement on the new trends of the technology in digitization initiatives.

"The process of digitization in academic libraries in our library has significant impacted our work environment, like engagement sa new technology" (Maam Zel, 4, Transcript 2, Page 4, Line 29-33)

(The process of digitization in academic libraries in our library has significantly impacted our work environment, such as engagement with new technology.)

Aside from technological enhancement and active engagement to digital trends that academic librarian should embrace with, there is also a need to explore and to have more capacity building on Dspace system due to its marc tags to secure the compatibility and accuracy of the digitized resources. Maam Prin shared her thoughts about the special features of digitization system, where personnel need to explore the digitization system of marc tags.

"Ang Dspace system mam dili pa kaayo, maglibog pa me asa ibutang ang mga tags, kay lahi ra siya sa ubang marc tags naa siya sariling tags pwede siya ma modify sa IT expert, pero limit lang kay open-source man siya, then naka-licensed pod siya (Maam Prin, Transcript

12, Page 23, Line 24-28)

(The DSpace system is still not that familiar to us. We are still confused about where to put the tags because it is different from other MARC tags. It has its own tags that can be modified by an IT expert, but it is limited since it is an open-source, and it is also licensed.)

Other predicaments shared by Sir Joe is the utilization of the special features of the marc tag system used for digitization initiatives.

“Potential risk kay accessibility, data traffic, metadata correct ba ang data like ang title basin didto na nabutang sa 700 lisod ma trace up, then yong last is ang ethical consideration” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 8, Line 26-29)

(The potential risk is accessibility, data traffic, and whether the metadata is correct, like the title might be placed in the 700 field, which would be hard to trace. Then the last concern is ethical consideration.)

Participant 4 also encountered the same dilemma on digitization process stating that there is a need to explore the marc tags on the digitized system.

“Roles might impact first is enhancing the Dspace support, para easier access kung nadigitized na yong book. Emphasizing the need of technological adeptness, so yong maka adopt tayo ng technology like Dspace unsaon siya pag-upload, unsaon pagdigitalized, collaboration also, then active engagement to digital trends” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 11-16)

(The roles that might be impacted, first, is enhancing DSpace support to make an easier access once the book is digitized. Emphasizing the need for technological adeptness, so we can adopt technology like DSpace on how to upload, how to digitize. Also, collaboration and active engagement with digital trends are important.)

Among the shared experiences of the academic librarians in digitization initiatives, the common factors were the lack of technical skills like the special features of the digitized system, intensive training and workshop for them to be familiar with the tags and embrace the advent of new trends of technology to attain a successful digitization efforts, and secure the easy access and retrieval of information without any glitches.

One common difficulty that academic librarian encountered was the lack of knowledge for digitization, particularly in utilizing the new trends on technology for digitization initiatives.

“On my part as a librarian, digitization of library resources is very useful sa millennial, but sa old generation parang mahirapan sila pero sa new generation ito yong gusto nila, kasi kahit saan ka as long as my internet you can access anything. Like ako old generation, so kailangan ko pang eh embrace yong technology, on how to do research siguro mahirapan pa ako on my part, kasi I’m not into techy person” 9 Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 6, Line 59-65)

(On my part as a librarian, the digitization of library resources is very useful for millennials, but for the older generation, it might be difficult. However, for the new generation, this is what they prefer because wherever you are, as long as there is internet, you can access anything. Like me, I am part of the older generation, so I still need to embrace technology. When it comes to doing research, I might find it difficult because I am not a techy person.)

Participant 4 also shared his thoughts about his difficulty in developing and enhancing more in the technological structure of the digitized resources. He stated that:

“For difficulties, we have budget, the technological structure also the staff expertise training in digitizing library resources” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 7, Line 1-6)

(I have difficulty on the budget, the technological infrastructure, and the staff expertise training in digitizing library resources.)

Also, Maam Ga shared her experiences on having difficulty for scanning in doing digitization initiative.

“Pinakamahirap dito is the result of the scanning, most of the materials here merong tayong mga 1970’s na collection ng newspaper. Yellowish na yong mga paper brittle, some is sira na yong pagesm and the result for scanning was blurry” Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 1-18)

(The most difficult part here is the result of the scanning. Most of the materials we have are from the 1970s, like newspaper collection. The paper is yellowish and brittle, and some pages are already damaged. As a result, it becomes blurry.)

Based on their responses, the difficulties experienced by academic librarians were the lack of knowledge for digitization initiatives, and having difficulty for scanning the resources which led to poor quality measures of contents and impedes on digitization progress. Digitization initiative is useless without enough knowledge in doing it, especially in the proper execution of the procedures to secure the accuracy and validity of the digitized resources.

Preservation Concerns. Preservation method was very crucial on the digitization efforts to secure streamline workflow, but in this scenario, academic librarians encountered difficulties on preservation methods like lack of data security, lack of preservation policies, and have insufficient file format as these are the major factors that impede digitization progress.

One of the common difficulties of academic librarians in digitization initiatives was the lack of data security like the insufficient back-up files that can affect the accessibility and usability of the digitized resources. In consonance to this, Maam Le shared her thoughts.

“It requires storage space for digital files” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 19, Line 4-5) (It requires storage space for digital files.)

Another participant shared his experiences about securing data back-ups on the digitized library resources. Sir Cio shared that

“If you don’t want to have that risk, aside from the data server of your digitized resources you must have a back-up server for your digitized resources” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 2, Line 29-32)

(If you do not want to have that risk, aside from the data server of your digitized resources, you must have a backup server for your digitized resources.)

The same dilemma was encountered by Maam Fe. Having no regular back-up of the files impedes a successful digitization initiative. She shared that

“Insufficient backup and disaster recovery mechanisms might worsen the risk of losing electronic materials” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 1-2, Line 49-50)

(Insufficient backup and disaster recovery mechanisms might worsen the risk of losing electronic materials.)

Maam Lin also experienced unsuccessful digitization efforts because of not having back-up those digitized collections, which led to loss of files that can no longer be accessed.

“Tapos ang worst is nacorrupt akong files so naga back-up nako” (Maam Lin, Transcript 8, Page 1, Line 14-15)

(And the worst part is my files got corrupted. So now, I always back them up.)

Moreover, aside from insufficient back-up files, data losses also can impede the security and longevity of the digitized collections, where Maam Fe shared her thoughts on this:

“Digital files are vulnerable to data loss or corruption caused by hardware malfunctions, software glitches, or cyber-attacks” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 1-2, Line 48-49)

(Digital files are vulnerable to data loss or corruption caused by hardware malfunctions, software glitches, or cyber-attacks.)

Also, Maam Ga also encountered the same delimma stating that

“One is the copyright consideration, aside from that is the data loss” (Maam Ga, Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 30-35)

(One is the copyright consideration, aside from that is the data loss.)

Not only Maam Fe and Maam Ga experienced data losses, but also Maam Han, which was the outdated format of the technology that caused the files to be corrupted. She shared that:

“Big risk because what if the technology stops working or sudden formatted? But to overcome with that concern, back up files is needed when we do digitization of resources” (Maam Han, Transcript 10, Page 1, Line 17-19)

(Big risk, because what if the technology stops working or is suddenly formatted? But to overcome that concern, backup files are needed when we digitize resources.)

Academic librarians doing digitization efforts were deeply challenged on the lack of data security, particularly on the insufficient file back-up due to budget constraints to acquire high-end equipment to suffice the storage space for digitized resources. Lack of data security can affect the accessibility and usability of the digitized materials.

One common hurdle encountered by academic librainans is the lack of preservation policies, especially the required adequate procedures to guarantee long-term preservation, which was the major factor to secure the accessibility and usability of the digitized resources in the future used. In relation to this, Maam Fe shared her experienced on this.

“Insufficient backup and disaster recovery mechanisms might worsen the risk of losing electronic materials. Integrating future technology will optimize procedures, improve user engagement, and guarantee the long-term preservation of digital resources” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 1-2, Line 49-50; Line 55-56)

(Insufficient backup and disaster recovery mechanisms might worsen the risk of losing electronic materials. Integrating future technology will optimize procedures, improve user engagement, and guarantee the long-term preservation of digital resources.)

In consonance with the statement of Maam Fe, participant 11 also experienced unstandardized procedure, which affects the digitization process flow.

“Ensure appropriate privacy and data protection measures/laws of the data loss. Lastly, is the long-term plan for maintenance, updates

and migration of digital content” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 5-8

(Ensure appropriate privacy and data protection measures/laws to address data loss. Lastly, there should be a long-term plan for the maintenance, updates, and migration of digital content.)

In connection to lack of preservation policies that require adequate procedures to guarantee long-term preservation, academic librarians also encountered challenges on the enhancement of digitization policy to secure the accuracy and validity of the digitized collections. Maam My shared her thought on this.

“Potential risk of course kapag naka digitized specially yong thesis and dissertation, madali lang yon siya eh copy and paste, kasi naka digitized na without citing the original author and claiming that it is yours so that’s the risk of digitizing library resources” (Maam My, Transcript 5, Page, Line 59-70)

(The potential risk, of course, when something is digitized, especially theses and dissertations, is that it is very easy to copy and paste since it is already digitized, without citing the original author and claiming it as your own. So that is the risk of digitizing library resources.)

In consonance to the ideas stated by Maam My, that it is easy to copy and paste the works of the others without securing an adequate policy to be implemented. Thus, Maam Ga seconded also her idea, to wit:

“Isa pa is the copyright consideration, hindi lang digitized ka ng digitized without permission. In terms of copyright kasi hindi siya pwede na yong na digitized mo send ka lang ng send sa mga users, paano nalang yong authors & publishing company, hindi na kumikita books nila” (Maam Ga, Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 7-10)

(Another consideration is copyright; you can not just digitize without permission. In terms of copyright, it is not acceptable to just send the digitized materials to users. What about the authors and publishing companies? They will not make money from their books anymore.)

The same predicament was shared by Maam Le, when it comes to the digitization policy enhancement. She stated that:

“For the copyright restrictions in digitizing library materials, need pa siya og permission sa owner” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 9-11)

(For the copyright restrictions in digitizing library materials, you still need to ask permission from the owner.)

Academic librarians have difficulty on the enhancement of digitization policy and lack of preservation policies as these factors impede on digitization initiatives because without proper procedures and policies, there is no smooth flow operations on it. Preservation policy is the basic guide to secure adequate procedures to guarantee long-term preservation and secure accessibility and usability of the digitized resources. Without the preservation policies, the digitization plans will be far from the ideal one.

Another common dilemma faced by academic librarians under preservation concerns is the insufficient file format specifically on poor scanning quality. Maam Ghie shared her experience on poor scanning quality.

“Pinakamahirap dito is the result of the scanning. Most of the materials here merong tayong mga 1970’s na collection ng Newspaper, yellowish na yong mga paper some is sira sira na yong pages” (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 1-18)

(The most difficult part here is the result of the scanning. Most of the materials we have include collections of newspapers from the 1970s, and the papers are yellowish, with some pages damaged.)

Moreover, in the insufficient file format that academic librarians faced, there is also a need to use a high-resolution equipment and proper scanning techniques to secure the quality control of the digitized resources. Maam Ghie her thoughts on the lack of a high-resolution equipment and proper scanning techniques in digitizing the library resources.

“Some is sira sira na yong pages and the result for scanning was blurry. Medyo mahirapan sila sa spacing ng scanning para makuha ang perfect angle, kasi cam scanner lang ginamit nila” (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 1-18)

(Some of the pages are already torn, and the result of the scanning was blurry. They had some difficulty with the spacing during the scanning to get the perfect angle because they only used a cam scanner.)

The same scenario was encountered by Maam Fe. The lack use of high-resolution equipment for digitization process leads to poor quality content of the digitized collections.

“Invest in high-quality scanning equipment and software to ensure accurate and high-resolution digital reproductions” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 70-71)

(Invest in high-quality scanning equipment and software to ensure accurate and high-resolution digital reproductions.)

Academic librarians need enhancement on metadata inputs to secure the accessibility and usability of the digitized resources, but Sir

Joe double checked first the metadata inputs before putting in the digitized collections. He shared on it:

“Also, yong metadata sa cataloging, kung pano natin eh classify sa Dspace system kung paano natin eh transcribe. Metadata correct ba ang data, like ang title basin didto na nabutang sa 700 lisod ma trace up” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 1-6; Line 26-29)

(Also, the metadata in cataloging, specifically how we classify it in the DSpace system and how we transcribe it. Is the metadata correct? The title might be possibly placed in the 700 field, which makes it difficult to trace.)

Maam Fe also shared her predicaments on the proper execution of the metadata inputs for easy access and retrieval the digitized information.

“Creating accurate and comprehensive metadata for digitized materials ensures they are easily searchable and accessible” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 1, Line 10-12)

Insufficient file format was experienced by the academic librarians due to some factors, such as, poor scanning quality and the lack of scanning techniques which affect the quality control measures of the digitized resources. In addition, the existing equipment is not in high resolution that results to uncleared contents. There is a need to double check and enhance on the metadata inputs also, if the data entries were correct on the specific marc tags of the digitized system.

Strategies of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources

Strategies refer to the creative approaches, methods, and techniques employed by academic librarians to navigate the challenges in transitioning the printed materials into digital format like prioritizing strategic planning for securing the accessibility and longevity of digitized resources to facilitate successful digitization projects. There are strategies that had been adapted in order to cope up with the difficulties encountered in digitizing library resources. Thus, when participants were asked about the strategies they had done in addressing their difficulties in digitizing library resources, three themes emerged: upgrade the technological infrastructure, training and professional development, and new digital preservation method.

Table 2. *Thematic Map on the Strategies Employed by Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources*

Strategies Employed by Academic Librarians to Overcome their Difficulties of Digitizing Library Resources
FIRST THEME
Upgrade of the Technological Infrastructure
Acquisition of digitization equipment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire a high-quality scanning equipment for better results • Acquire software for quality control measures of the contents
Use appropriate hardware application
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use editor software to enhance the quality control of the content • Use cellular phones instead of scanner • Re-take blurry pictures to get the perfect angle and have a clear content
Funding allocations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate budget allocation for the digitization efforts • Sufficient funds for software enhancement of the contents
Improved Internet connectivity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install high speed internet connectivity • Secure an accurate domain name
SECOND THEME
Training and Professional Development
In-depth staff training
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate and train staff in digitization process • Attend seminars and workshops • Conduct in-house trainings
Fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge exchange with peers • Collaborate with IT expert and database supplier
THIRD THEME
New Digital Preservation Methods
Crafting and Implementation of New policies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate long-term planning for maintaining digitization efforts • Planning for ethical consideration • Adequate policy procedures on digitization
Appropriate Digital Curation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ meticulous handling techniques of materials for digitization • Utilize high-end applications for the digitized resources

Upgrade of the Technological Infrastructure. It is a key emergent theme in the strategies employed by academic librarians to overcome the challenges in digitizing library resources. As libraries transition from traditional to digital formats, the need for advanced technology becomes crucial to manage and provide access to vast collections of digitized resources. Thus, acquisition of digitization equipment, the use of appropriate hardware application, funding allocations, and improved internet connectivity are the significant factors to secure the accessibility, usability, and validity of the digitized collections. Secured funding and the selection of appropriate hardware applications are the cornerstones of sustaining digitization efforts. Adequate budget allocation allows for the acquisition of high-end

equipment, which can enhance the quality image of the contents. In essence, the technological infrastructure serves as the backbone of a library's digital transformation, directly influencing the effectiveness of digitization efforts.

One common clustered theme under strategies employed by academic librarians is the acquisition of digitization equipment in order to secure the high-quality content of the digitized collections. Maam Fe shared her thought on this.

"Resource allocation which allocate resources efficiently, balancing the needs of digitization with other library functions" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 74-76)

In relation, Maam Prin added that to acquire high-quality, scanning equipment will enhance the results. She shared:

"Another strategy, since scanner man pod among problema is magpurchased pod me og new scanner flatbed type. The good thing about sa flatbed kay kung tarungon nimo pag-cut og pagfeed dali ra kaayo" (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 1, Line 40-42)

(Another strategy, since one of the problems is the scanner, is that we might purchase a new flatbed type scanner. The good thing about the flatbed is that if you cut and feed it properly, it is very easy to use.)

The same strategy was employed by Maam Fe. She expressed that:

"Invest in high-quality scanning equipment" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 70-71)

Academic librarians face various challenges when digitizing library resources, and one of the key strategies to overcome these difficulties is through the acquisition of appropriate digitization equipment. To ensure high-quality digital versions of physical materials, librarians invest in advanced scanning equipment that can handle various types of documents, from fragile manuscripts to modern texts. High-resolution scanners are essential in capturing clear, detailed images, which are crucial for preserving the integrity of the original materials.

The use of appropriate hardware application can help to fast track the process in digitization efforts and save time and efforts in the part of the librarian. Thus, to acquire software for digitization initiatives was the strategy employed by Maam Fe, in order to ensure the quality control measures of the contents.

"Invest in software to ensure accurate and high-resolution digital reproductions" (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 70-71)

Another strategy to improve the quality of the digitized collections was the use of editing software, which Ma'am Prin employed during the digitization process. She expressed that

"Watching video tutorials when it comes to digitizing library resources, kung unsaon pagpanindot sa quality sa image or sa documents" (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 1, Line 31-33)

(Watching video tutorials when it comes to digitizing library resources, on how to improve the quality of images or documents.)

In connection, the use of cellular phones instead of scanner is another technique employed by Maam Ghie. She expressed that:

"Since ang scanning required a good quality of all taking picture of the materials, we need a high-resolution type of cellphones. As I mention kanina dati nag recommend ako ng camera pero mahirapan sila gumamit, kasi recommended talaga perfect angle so they opted to used cellphone" (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 2, Line 35-42)

(Since scanning requires good quality in taking pictures of the materials, we need high-resolution cell phones. As I mentioned earlier, I once recommended a camera, but they had difficulty using it because it really required a perfect angle. So, they opted to use cell phones instead.)

Maam Ga added, that instead of using a high-end scanning device, she used mobile scanner for scanning resources and converted them into digital format. Hence, there is no barrier in digitization efforts to the librarian's initiative.

"Like now, we are scanning some of the printed resources na needed, especially yong mga nag-iisang books na demand sa mga users. So ang ginawa namin is scanning using our mobile phone (cam scanner). So, our strategy is kung ano lang yong available na resources needed for digitization like phones, yon lang muna ginagamit namin" (Maam Ga, Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 11-18; Line 52-54)

(Right now, we are scanning some of the printed resources that are needed, especially the unique books that are in demand from users. So what we did is scan using our mobile phone (cam scanner). Our strategy is to only use the available resources needed for digitization, like phones. That is what we are using for now.)

Additionally, digitizing library resources can be quite challenging without adequate devices. However, this does not hinder the realization of digitization efforts. Instead, librarians employ techniques to ensure clear and vivid content by re-capturing blurry images until they achieve the perfect angle for clearer results. Ma'am Ghie shared her thoughts on this.

"Kailangan yong perfect angle, dapat walang mawala na content ng newspaper para very clear at hindi blurry. So, delete and take a perfect angle again" (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 4, Line 82-84)

(The perfect angle is needed; no content from the newspaper should be lost to ensure that it is very clear and not blurry. So, delete and take a perfect angle again.)

Another strategy employed by the academic librarians was to use appropriate hardware and software application that provide advanced features for enhancing image quality like cropping, adjusting brightness and contrast, and even correcting minor distortions, which led to good representation of the original one. Also, retaking blurry pictures can improve clarity of the contents, too.

Funding allocation for digitizing library resources is a critical component that ensures the successful implementation of digitization initiatives, where acquiring the necessary hardware and equipment, such as high-resolution scanners, cameras, and storage devices, are essential for capturing and preserving library materials in digital formats. In consonance to this statement, Maam Fe shared her thoughts on this:

“Resource allocation which allocate resources efficiently, balancing the needs of digitization with other library functions” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 74-76)

In addition, libraries often invest in software and licensing for specialized applications that facilitate image processing to convert scanned images into searchable text. Maam Prin employed this strategy to enhance the content of the resources like an original one. She stated that:

“Naa may yellow stain ang paper, before namo na siya eh save naka edit napod siya daan, as much as possible pwede pa nimo na siya ma brush sa editor software para ma enhanced ang iyang texture, brightness, contrast” (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 2, Line 46-48)

The paper has a yellow stain, and before we saved it, it was already edited. If possible, we can still brush it in the editing software to enhance its texture, brightness, and contrast.)

An adequate budget allocation is essential to support various aspects of the digitization process, ensuring that libraries can effectively convert physical materials into digital formats. This includes not only the purchase of necessary equipment, such as high-resolution scanners and cameras, but also allocate sufficient funds for software enhancements, which play a significant role in improving the quality and accessibility of digitized content.

Improved internet connectivity is an essential factor in the successful digitization of library resources, as it directly impacts the efficiency and accessibility of digital content. High-speed internet facilitates the rapid upload and download of large digital files, ensuring that library staff can swiftly digitize materials and make them available to users. In consonance to this statement, Maam Le shared her thoughts.

“Increase the access speed pod sa internet, para dali lang ma access ng mga users ang mga nadigitized na collections” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 18-19)

(Increase the internet access speed so that users can easily access the digitized collections.)

In addition, securing an accurate domain name of the digitized collections is necessary to easily navigate the digitized resources and retrieval of information. Maam Ghie said that:

“Since meron naman internet connection and functional naman yong domain name ng mga newspaper namin searchable lang man siya” (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 4-5, Line 91-92)

(Since we have an internet connection and our newspaper domain name is functional, it is searchable.)

Based on the experience of the participants, improved internet connectivity is vital for the effective digitization of library resources, as it significantly enhanced user access and overall operational efficiency. Installing high-speed internet connectivity allows library personnel to upload and download large digital files swiftly, ensuring that digitized materials are available to users without delays.

Training and Professional Development. This refers to comprehensive staff training program which significantly contributed to a successful digitization initiative. In-depth training activities like educating staff on the digitization process, attending seminars and workshops, conducting in-house training sessions and fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among experts and co-librarians will lead to an efficient and effective digitization process.

One common technique to surpass the difficulties is in-depth staff training. It has a great contribution on digitization process. Sir Cio shared his thoughts on this.

“To educate your staff in digitization, and then from among your staff is there anyone who could sustain your digitalization of resources? because when you digitized resources is not the end of it, but you have to organized it as well according to the usual cataloging classification and so on and so forth, and then you connect into your data library system. One is that is continuing education or self-education as part of the librarians. What are on the current trends in digitalization of library materials and resources by reading online or printed materials” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 3, Line 55-59; Line 66-69)

The same scenario was employed by Maam Fe. Staff training and development is vital to stay abreast with the current trends on

digitization process.

“Staff training and development to provide ongoing training in digitization to keep them updated on the latest technologies, standards, and best practices” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 77-78)

Also, Sir Gar shared his thoughts about individual learning about digitization process. He shared that:

“Wala pa gyud, na learn jud ni siya tungod sa pandemic naka learn ang mga tao” (Sir Gar, Transcript 7, Page1, Line 43)

(Not yet, this was really learned because of the pandemic; people have learned.)

In connection, seminars and workshops on digitization initiatives is one of the techniques to contribute on digitization efforts, at the same time augment the knowledge of the library personnel on the proper execution of digitization efforts. Maam Fe expressed her experience.

“Workshop for librarians in digitization, kay dili man gud tanang librarian kabalo mo scan og karaan na mga materials. Need to attend seminars and trainings” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 35-39)

(Workshops for librarians in digitization are necessary, because not all librarians know how to scan old materials. They need to attend seminars and training sessions.)

Also, Maam Prin encouraged her library staff to attend seminars and trainings to gain more knowledge on digitization process. She shared that:

“Attending seminars and trainings and in-service training about digitization” (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 2, Line 49)

Additionally, conducting in-house trainings has a significant impact on digitization efforts, as library personnel gain knowledge on the proper execution on the digitization process. Maam Prin attested on this.

“Hands-on training, if naa kay mga queries you can address mga concerns sa IT expert. Aside from hands-on training, syempre ma explore sa Dspace system and in-house training and workshops murag four times na me nag training ana” (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 1, Line 31-33)

(Hands-on training. If you have any queries, you can address your concerns to the IT expert. Aside from hands-on training, of course, you can explore the DSpace system and participate in in-house training and workshops. We have training for about four times.)

The same strategy was employed by Sir Joe. He expressed that:

“Mag invites me og expert resource person sa Dspace system in-house training lang to discuss about it, kung unsaon pag-operate og unsay use og ibutang nimo sa Dspace, unsa ang pwede pa mabuhay ni Dspace when it comes to digitizing library resources” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 3, Line 52-54)

(We will invite an expert resource person for the DSpace system in-house training to discuss how to operate it, what its uses are, and what can be added to DSpace. They will also explain what DSpace can do when it comes to digitizing library resources.)

In-depth staff training has a great contribution to secure the accessibility and usability of the digitized collections. Conducting comprehensive training like attending seminars, workshops, and even an in-house training can lead into an efficient and effective digitization process.

Another clustered theme strategies employed by academic librarians under training and professional development is fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing, which is essential factor for maximizing the efficiency and effectiveness of digitization efforts. Maam My shared her thoughts on knowledge exchange with peers.

“Basically, we seek advice part of the plan, siguro kung meron talagang mga delicate or fragile materials na eh digitized, I think that’s the time we need to hire someone who is an expert on it. Yes, we have Mastlinet one vision diba ang vision natin one access Mindanao so basically part yong digitization ng mga resources natin even DACUN meron din so my collaborative efforts, and may consortium na ginahimo” (Maam My, Transcript 5, Page 3, Line 98-100; Line 117-120)

(Basically, we seek advice as part of the plan. Maybe if there are really delicate or fragile materials to be digitized, I think that is the time we need to hire someone who is an expert in it. Yes, we have Mastlinet, and our vision is 'One Access Mindanao,' so digitization of our resources is part of that. Even DACUN is involved, so there are collaborative efforts, and a consortium is being formed.)

Ma'am Han also shared her experience, stating that she sought guidance from her co-workers who were already well-versed and were fully established in digitization efforts. She shared that:

“As for my concerns about my works, I am asking or seeking information to my co-librarian that are my college classmates because they are employed in universities that is innovative and has more experience about digitizing library resources” (Maam Han, Transcript 10, Page 1, Line 36-39)

(As for my concerns about my work, I am asking or seeking information from my co-librarians, who are my college classmates, because they are employed in universities that are innovative and have more experience in digitizing library resources.)

As one of the strategies applied by Maam Fe, to have a successful digitization effort was to engage and communicate with the people in her community. She shared that:

“Engage with the community to raise awareness about digitization efforts and encourage feedback to improve services” (Maam Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 78-80)

(Engage with the community to raise awareness about digitization efforts and encourage feedback to improve services.)

In connection, Maam Zel added that collaboration with IT expert and database supplier is one way of addressing difficulty on digitization. She expressed that:

“Collaborate with the IT expert and coordinate with the online database supplier to conduct orientation, base sa particular services na among gi avail sa ilaha like explanation of the product on how to access” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 38-41; Line 53-57)

(Collaborate with the IT expert and coordinate with the online database supplier to conduct an orientation. This orientation will focus on specific services offered by the supplier, including explanations of the product and how to access it.)

Knowledge sharing within these collaborations helps standardize processes, ensuring that digitized resources are accessible and usable across different systems and institutions. It also promotes the creation of common platforms and technologies, facilitating easier access to a wide array of resources for users. Through networking with librarians from other institutions or attending professional conferences, academic librarians can gain exposure to different approaches, tools, and technologies used in digitization. This exchange of ideas helps them stay updated on the latest trends and methods, enabling them to adopt solutions that have been successfully implemented.

New Digital Preservation Methods. Proactive planning on preservation methods and policies for maintaining digitization efforts are the key to success in ensuring the longevity and accessibility of digitized materials. Through these steps, digitization initiatives can not only transform information into a readily accessible digital format but also guarantee its preservation for future generations. With this, crafting and implementing preservation policies has significant factor to guarantee the accessibility, usability and longevity of the digitized resources. As shared by Maam My, incorporate long-term planning will secure the accessibility of the digitized materials.

“We prepare a plan dili pwedeng sa utak lang lahat. That is why we come up a plan, so with that plan meron kaming mother plan for digitization we called it the knowledge management project plan” (Maam My, Transcript 5, Page 1, Line 22-24)

(We prepare a plan; it cannot all just be in our heads. That is why we came up with a plan, and with that plan, we have a master plan for digitization which we call the knowledge management project plan.)

Maam Zel also shared her experience that strategic plan is one way to overcome those difficulties encountered in digitizing library resources. She mentioned that:

“The strategies I have integrated in my strategic plan, and inclusion also in my annual work financial plan specifically the maintenance of digitization, and of course information literacy” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 34-37)

Maam Lin's strategy for overcoming difficulties in digitizing library resources was strategic planning. She believed that by creating a plan of action, every challenge could be addressed effectively. She stated that:

“The strategies or actions to be implemented in coping the concerns, when it comes to digitization initiatives is made a proposal plan, strategies plan” (Maam Lin, Transcript 8, Page 1, Line 25-26)

Maam Le encountered a similar scenario, where crafting a strategic plan for converting printed materials into digital format was crucial for ensuring a successful digitization process. She shared that:

“One of the strategies about digitizing library resources is the back-up files, strategic planning related to implementation of REDMAS database which needs budget” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 32-33)

Planning for ethical considerations is crucial for ensuring the accessibility of digitized resources while safeguarding them from plagiarism and copyright infringement. This approach emphasizes responsible stewardship of information, ensuring that digitized materials are shared equitably and legally. In line with this, Maam Zel shared her thoughts on the matter:

“The approach is nagcoordinate me sa research division office for ethical consideration” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 42-46)

(The approach involved coordinating with the research division office for ethical consideration.)

Another participant emphasized the importance of ethical considerations in digitizing library resources. She shared that:

“Another strategy is use plagiarism checker, for checking research output to ensure copyright issues” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 34)

Incorporating long-term planning for maintaining digitization efforts and for ethical consideration have a significant impact on digitization process because planning was the basic asset on digitization to have streamline workflows. Without it, there is no assurance to secure the longevity of resources.

Another appropriate preservation method on digitization process was the adequate policy procedures on digitization that guides the creation of accurate and comprehensive metadata for digitized resources. Ma'am Fe shared her thought on this.

“Providing instruction to staff members on the correct procedures for handling fragile items” (Ma'am Fe, Transcript 6, Page2-3, Line 91-96)

Ma'am Fe also shared her experience, emphasizing that to ensure the accessibility of digitized resources, there must be an adequate policy and procedure in place for prioritizing which resources should be digitized first. She shared that

“Develop a clear prioritization strategy to determine which collections to digitize first based on criteria such as fragility, frequency of use, and importance” (Ma'am Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 68-69)

Additionally, when digitizing library resources, it is necessary to secure multiple backups of the digitized materials. This way, if the system collapses, the digitized collections can be easily retrieved and accessed. Ma'am Prin shared her thoughts on this:

“Naa me specific computer unit na for digitization lang siya, na naka store store tanang files tapos naa pod me back-up sa hard drive. Dili siya pwede isa lang ang imong back-up, dapat naa jud siya multiple back-ups” (Ma'am Prin, Transcript 12, Page 1, Line 38-39)

(We have a specific computer unit dedicated solely for digitization, where all files are stored, and we also have backups on a hard drive. You cannot just have one backup. It is essential to have multiple backups.)

Appropriate digital curation is crucial for digitizing library resources, as it ensures that digital materials are organized, preserved, and accessible over the long term. Additionally, it supports compliance with legal and ethical standards related to copyright and data protection. This practice enables libraries to uphold their responsibilities in managing sensitive information while providing public access, all the while maintaining the integrity and authenticity of the digitized resources. The right methods to secure the longevity and preservation of the digitized resources employed meticulous handling techniques of materials for digitization, and utilized high-end applications for the digitized resources. Ma'am Prin shared her thoughts on this:

“Handle with care lang siya, ana lang para ma preserve pa ang collections” (Ma'am Lin, Transcript 8, Page1, Line 27-30)

(Just handle it with care. That is all, to help preserve the collections.)

Meticulous handling of fragile resources is necessary to ensure clear contents. As what Sir Joe shared that

“Handle with care lang, sa katong mga thesis and dissertation na karaan na kaayo na brittle and yellowish na ang paper” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 3, Line 46-49)

(Just handle with care, especially for those old theses and dissertations that have very brittle and yellowish paper.)

The same strategy was employed by Ma'am Fe. Handling with care was essential factor to preserve the longevity of the digitized resources.

“Preserving delicate or fragile objects, such as ancient manuscripts, old pictures, or brittle papers, necessitates meticulous handling to prevent harm to the originals” (Ma'am Fe, Transcript 6, Page 2-3, Line 81-82)

Ma'am Ghie also shared the same strategies in handling fragile materials. Handling with care is very necessary to prevent further brittleness of the paper.

“Careful talaga yong staff, dapat yong kamay nila walang water, dapat dry talaga yong kamay nila” (Ma'am Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 4, Line 85-90)

(The staff must be very careful; their hands should be free of moisture, and they should keep their hands completely dry.)

Moreover, utilizing high-end applications for the digitized resource has a significant impact to enhance the quality image of the collections. Sir Joe expressed his thoughts:

“Naggamit me og high-end application para ma enhanced ang picture or maklaro ang content” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 3, Line 46-49)

(We used high-end application to enhance the quality image and to have clearer contents.)

Also, Ma'am Le stated that fragile resources need a specialized scanning equipment for the proper preservation of it.

“Naa siyay specific scanner equipment para sa delicate and fragile materials, so ang among scanner naa siya camera scanner para dili matandang while on-going scanning” (Ma'am Le, Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 35-38)

(It has specific scanning equipment for delicate and fragile materials, so our scanner has a camera scanner to prevent contact while scanning is in progress.)

Based on the participants' point of view, proper preservation safeguards the accuracy and trustworthiness of digitized materials, at the same time ensures the authenticity and integrity on it. One of the fundamental aspects of digital curation is the employment of meticulous handling techniques for materials designated for digitization. This careful approach minimizes the risk of damage, particularly for delicate and fragile items, such as ancient manuscripts and brittle papers. Academic librarians must be trained in these techniques to safeguard the integrity of the original materials while preparing them for digitization. Additionally, utilizing high-end applications enhances the quality of the digitized resources. These advanced tools allow for better image enhancement, resolution adjustments, and content clarification, ensuring that the digital representations are as accurate and useful as possible.

Forms of Support that Academic Librarians Needed from the Administration

Forms of support refer to the initiatives of the academic librarians that the administration will entice and support to have great contribution in realizing the transformation of printed resources into digitization format. It also refers to the various ways the administration can assist librarians in achieving successful digitization projects. This support is important in overcoming the difficulties associated with digitization, ensuring that the process is effective and sustainable. Thus, the participants were asked about the form of support they need and the following themes emerged, namely; increase financial resource allocation, administrative support for policy development, and expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections.

Table 3. *Thematic Map on the Forms of Support Needed by Academic Librarians from the Administration*

Forms of Support that Academic Librarians Needed from the Administration
<p>FIRST THEME</p> <p>Increase Financial Resource Allocation</p> <p>Financial support for staff development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support for staff capacity building • Increase funds for benchmarking • Enhance budget for staff training through attendance to seminars, trainings etc. <p>Provision of sufficient funds for technological infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate budget allocation for acquisition of technological facilities • Securing sufficient funding to cover operational costs, etc. • Need adequate budget for digitization
<p>SECOND THEME</p> <p>Administrative Support for Policy Development</p> <p>Crafting and implementing digitization policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for digitization efforts to have security measures • New policies reflect the president's commitment to regenerative future thinking • Administration helps enhance policy changes for digitization initiatives <p>Need for administrative support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assurances of support from the administration • School president's plan to have a library inspection to determine the lacking facilities • Administrative policy is in need to help implement and realize the digitization project • Support from the technical personnel for data security and privacy
<p>THIRD THEME</p> <p>Expanding Collaboration for Resource Sharing of Digitized Collections</p> <p>Collaboration and resource sharing initiatives of digitized resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Come up with the memorandum of understanding or memorandum of agreement with other institutions on the use of digital resources and resource sharing initiatives • Consortium activities among librarians in Mindanao academic libraries • Policy making guidelines on the consortia activity of the library <p>Librarians' initiative to collaborate with experts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Librarians' initiative to tap and collaborate with the experts in the field for the digitization implementation projects • Connect with IT expert for digital preservation and conversion of materials

Increase Financial Resource Allocation. This emergent theme is one of the forms of support needed by the academic librarians from their administrators. Having adequate financial resource allocation will significantly contribute to staff development, acquisition of high-end equipment on digitization at the same time additional manpower to do on the digitization efforts and other operational costs needed for digitization project.

One common clustered theme under forms of support needed is the financial support for staff development to gain more knowledge as to the proper execution of the digitized collections. Maam Zel shared a thought about financial support for staff capacity building.

“Increase financial support for professional development, pero kanang in-house lang like mag invite lang ta like consultant or IT expert, kay para dili kaayo gasto” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 3, Line 58-61)

(Increase financial support for professional development, but it should be in-house, like inviting consultants or IT experts, to keep costs down.)

In connection, funds for benchmarking are essential for any digitization project to benchmark best practices. Ma'am My mentioned that: "Siguro ang successful na financial support from the admin, ang ilahang pag-enhance nla sa budget para library sa internationalization na initiatives sa university. Kay diha mas naka benchmark me og mga international libraries, makit-an pod namo ang ilang best practices pagdating sa digitization initiatives" (Ma'am My, Transcript 5, Page 4, Line 153-156)

(Perhaps the successful financial support from the administration is their enhancement of the budget for the library's internationalization initiatives at the university. This allows us to benchmark against international libraries and observe their best practices regarding digitization initiatives.)

Ma'am Le also added that benchmarking funds is a crucial factor that the administration should consider when it comes to digitization initiatives.

"Number one is the increase financial support jud, to conduct benchmarking from other libraries implementing digitization of library resources" (Ma'am Le, Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 44-45; Line 51-53)

(Number one is to increase financial support to conduct benchmarking with other libraries implementing digitization of library resources)

The form of support needed is an increased budget for staff training through attendance at seminars and workshops to gain a broader understanding of the proper execution of digitization efforts. Sir Gar shared his thoughts on this.

"The role of administration is open ang mga staff sa mga trainings, specifically related on digitization seminar and workshops" (Sir Gar, Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 49-50)

(The role of the administration is to support the staff in attending training, specifically related to digitization seminars and workshops)

In digitizing library resources, academic librarians needed support from the administrator such as adequate financial support for staff development, staff capacity building like attending seminars and workshops to acquire knowledge and be aware of the modern approaches on digitization. This is to improve the quality of the digitized materials and also to boost staff confidence and job satisfaction. Additionally, funds for benchmarking are essential for any digitization project, as they allow library personnel to study and compare their processes with those of other institutions. This exposure to successful models can lead to the adoption of innovative approaches that improve overall efficiency and effectiveness.

Another form of support needed for digitization initiatives is the provision of sufficient funds for technological infrastructure, particularly for the acquisition of technological facilities. Sir Joe shared his thoughts on this.

"Financial support gihapon maam, kay sila man magprovide sa atong budget para magpalit og mga equipments maam. Kay kung dili pod sila mohatag sa budget dili man pod marealized ang project" (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 3, Line 58-61)

(Financial support is still important, because they provide our budget for purchasing equipment. If they do not allocate the budget, the project cannot be realized.)

In connection, Sir Gar shared that securing sufficient funding to cover operational costs and others will be a great of help on digitization efforts, since budget was the root cause of all to realize an efficient and effective digitization process.

"Funds jud everything magstart jud sa funds. Tungod sa funds pwede ta ipadala sa training, palit equipment and etc" (Sir Gar, Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 44-45)

(Funds are essential; everything starts with funds. Because of the funds, we can send staff to training, purchase equipment, and so on.)

Aside from securing sufficient funding for technological facilities, there is a need for an adequate budget to hire additional skilled personnel for digitization. Without a skilled staff, the digitization process is unlikely to be successful.

"Number one is the allocation of budget, and then the additional manpower or skilled staff" (Ma'am Ga, Transcript 9, Page2, Line 80)

Academic librarians needed support on provision of sufficient funds for technological infrastructure, additional qualified personnel, and high-end equipment to surpass on the digitization hindrances. Adequate budget allocation for the acquisition of technological facilities, such as high-quality scanners, servers, and software, is vital to ensure that the digitization process is efficient and effective. These tools are necessary to handle various materials and formats, thereby preserving valuable resources for future access. Moreover, securing sufficient funding to cover operational costs, including maintenance and upgrades of equipment, and secure long-term sustainability of digitization projects. Without proper funding, libraries may encounter technical issues that could impede on digitization efforts.

Administrative Support for Policy Development. Administrative support plays a key role in establishing a clear vision and measurable goals for digitization efforts like crafting criteria and the implementation of digitization policies in securing security measures.

Specifically, crafting and implementing digitization policies with strong security measures will ensure a smooth transition to a digital

environment and to safeguard valuable information. This point of view was supported by Sir Cio.

“It is very important policy changes. Like for instance I’m looking now the possibility of digitizing thesis and putting them online free of charge for anyone to read, access and etc, but we have to put security measures to these resources to put a watermark” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 4, Line83-87)

Additionally, new policies reflecting the president's commitment to regenerative future thinking was a great support to fully implement the digitization efforts. Sir Gar shared that

“Naa silay policy changes specially our president is naka focus siya sa regenerative future thinking, focus on more new technology and etc” (Sir Gar, Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 46-48)

(They have policy changes, especially since our president is focused on regenerative future thinking and on incorporating more new technologies, among other things.)

Administration will not just support on sufficient budget but also help enhance policy changes for digitization initiatives to ensure smooth flow operations. Sir Joe said that

“Policies and guidelines changes, sa pagdigitized sa collection gina improve pa namo, kung naa changes sa digitization process naay possibility na ma change jud pod ang policies and guidelines” (Sir Joe, Transcript 4, Page 3, Line 62-64)

(We are still improving the policies and guidelines for digitizing the collection. If there are changes in the digitization process, there is a possibility that the policies and guidelines will also change.)

Strong administrative support is vital for developing and implementing effective digitization policies. It ensures strategic planning and a well-developed policy making to overcome hindrances on digitization.

Aside from crafting and implementing digitization policies, there is also a need for administrative support regarding budget allocation for the project planning and execution, where the administration should look into. This was supported by Maam Zel.

“None ma’am, wala pa man so far kay as is pa man mo support lang sila” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 3, Line 62-64)

(None so far ma’am. They are still supporting us.)

Maam Han shared the form of support from her administration. The school president planned to have a library inspection to determine the lacking facilities, and to secure the digitization equipments and others. She stated that:

“There’s none, but the school president planned to conduct inspection to the library to check the lacking facilities” (Maam Han, Transcript 10, Page 2, Line 49-50)

Additionally, crafting administrative policies would help realize the digitization project, as academic librarians require assistance from the administration. Maam Zel shared her thoughts on this.

“When we speak in digitizing library resources, maybe they are also provisionary about the plan in our library. Where it will be included in our strategic plan in the institution. Mag-unsang man kung naa tay plan, kung dili sila interested our plan is dili jud siya magsuccess” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 4, Line 68-71)

(When we talk about digitizing library resources, they may also be concern about the plan for our library, which will be included in our institution's strategic plan.)

Ma'am My also shared her experience regarding the policy changes related to digitization efforts, which received support from the administration. She mentioned that

“Yes policy changes, kung mag-implement ka og digitization mo follow jud ng mga policies, kasi nag-implement ta og something new part sa imong innovation sa inyong services. Unya kana na innovation naa na siyay specific protocol, mga policies na dapat eh in place na dapat eh follow” (Maam My, Transcript 5, Page 4, Line 136-141)

(Yes, policy changes are necessary. When you implement digitization, you must follow the policies because we are introducing something new as part of the innovation in your services. This innovation will have specific protocols and policies that must be in place and must be followed.)

A similar scenario was encountered by Ma'am Ga regarding policy changes in the digitization process, wherein the administration was in the process of taking action. She shared that:

“Sa policy changes wala man. Siguro naay plan ang admin to continue or mag gawa ng policy or other initiatives for digitization, pero as of now wala pa silay move. Since naa pa siguro sila laing giprioritize. As for now wala paman, but I know soon they will make some move or initiatives to continue implementing for digitization” (Maam Ga, Transcript 9, Page2-3, Line 81-84)

(There are no policy changes as of the the moment. Perhaps the administration has plans to develop policies or other initiatives for

digitization, but as of now, they have not made any moves, maybe because they are prioritizing other matters. For now, nothing has been done, but I believe they will soon take action or implement initiatives to continue the digitization process.)

Moreover, when it comes to digitization efforts, it needs technical personnel for data security and privacy which the administration should look into. Technical personnel are essential for establishing and maintaining robust security measures that protect digitized resources from unauthorized access, cyber threats, etc. Maam Prin shared her thoughts on this.

“Yes maam, in terms of data privacy and data security mao jud na importante. So wala pa jud policy para sa digitization, para matabangan ang digitization ang administration kinahanglan jud maghimo og mga policies para sa data privacy, and data restrictions. Ppara pod sa personal information mga book like procedures how to implement digitization, how to access digitization” (Maam Prin, Transcript 12, Page 2, Line 55-58)

(Yes, ma'am, when it comes to data privacy and data security, that is indeed very important. So, there are still no policies in place for digitization. To support digitization, the administration really needs to create policies for data privacy and data restrictions, as well as procedures for handling personal information, such as how to implement digitization and how to access digitized materials.)

Having a well-defined policy is essential for a successful library digitization project. Hence, the administration has proactive initiatives to do library inspections for the lacking facilities. Additionally, acknowledging the need for technical support from IT personnel ensures the security and privacy of digitized data. Technical personnel play a crucial role in maintaining the integrity, confidentiality, and security of digitization initiatives. Their expertise allows organizations to leverage the advantages of digital transformation while safeguarding sensitive information and complying with legal standards.

Expanding Collaboration for Resource Sharing of Digitized Collections. Expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections gained more knowledge and resources for everyone. Collaboration allows libraries to share their unique collections, creating a vast virtual library accessible to a wider audience. Expanding their research and learning opportunities, they need to come up with the memorandum of understanding or memorandum of agreement with other institutions on the use of digital resources and resource sharing. Sir Cio shared that

“Sharing knowledge and collaboration is to come up with the memorandum of understanding, or memorandum of agreement with other institutions on the use of digital resources, digitalization project and access of digitize resources” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 4-5, Line 90-96)

In connection, Maam Zel stated that having consortium activities among librarians in Mindanao academic libraries can expand research to users.

“Consortium among librarians in Mindanao through signing MOA, participating initiated activities of the association through moral support and encouragement from our administration” (Maam Zel, Transcript 2, Page 3, Line 65-67)

Sir Cio added that expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections will support in crafting policies and guidelines on the consortia activity to clarify the terms and condition as well as the goals. He expressed that:

“Maybe they could start a research journal in different institutions, they can on that instead of selling it to book publishers, and book dealers. They can come up with that project and then share it to the different network members, and whatever mode of arrangement” (Sir Cio, Transcript 1, Page 4-5, Line 90-96)

Expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections is a very important form of support from the administrations. By fostering collaboration and resource sharing, libraries can create a richer digital landscape, empowering users and expanding access to knowledge. By working together, institutions can pool their knowledge, share best practices, and access a broader range of technical skills. Collaborative networks, such as library consortia or inter-institutional partnerships, enable participants to learn from one another's successes and failures, accelerating the development of robust digitization programs.

Aside from collaboration and resource sharing initiatives of digitized resources, librarians' initiative to collaborate experts is another form of support. This can be done by tapping and collaborating with the experts in the field of digitization implementation projects. This point of view was supported by Maam Le.

“Initiative sa librarian na makig-collaborate sa administration, kung unsay implementation na gi-initiate sa librarians. So far wala pa me nadiscuss sa admin about sa pagdigitized ng collections, pero in the future maam na maging smart library na kami” (Maam Le, Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 48-50)

(It is an initiative taken by librarians to collaborate with the administration regarding the implementations initiated by the librarians. So far, we have not discussed digitizing the collections with the admin, but in the future, ma'am, we aim to become a smart library.)

Maam Ghie added that connecting with IT expert for digital preservation and conversion of materials were great forms of support that contributed to their successful digitization effort. She shared:

“To overcome difficulties in our digitization, since the project was about to finish, I will talk to sir Johnny kung anong mga kailangan

niya. Kung ano ba yong application gamitin niya to permanently store the digitized collections, kasi we can help them to tap our IT expert in our library to assists and help him” (Maam Ghie, Transcript 3, Page 6, Line 119-125)

(To overcome difficulties in our digitization, since the project is about to finish, I will talk to Sir Johnny about what he needs. I will ask him which application he plans to use to permanently store the digitized collections because we can help him by connecting him with our IT expert in the library for assistance.)

With this, overcoming the difficulties of academic librarians associated with the digitization of library materials is crucial for realizing the full benefits of digital libraries and ensuring that valuable cultural, educational, and informational resources are preserved and accessible for future generations of users. Physical materials are susceptible to damage, decay, and loss due to factors like environmental conditions, natural disasters, and mishandling. Digitization creates durable digital copies that safeguard the content from physical degradation.

Adding on, strategies in digitization play a crucial part for the successful transformation of traditional library resources into digital formats. Effective strategies ensure that digitization efforts are efficient, sustainable, and aligned with the mission and goals of the institution. Digitization can be resource-intensive, requiring significant investment in technology, staff training, and infrastructure. A well-planned strategy helps optimize the use of available funds and resources, reducing waste and unnecessary expenditures.

Finally, support needed by academic librarians in Davao region from their school administrators play a key role in securing and allocating funds for digitization projects. This includes investment in necessary technology, software, and personnel. Adequate funding is essential for acquiring high-quality equipment, storage solutions, and the ongoing costs associated with digital preservation. Also, support for training library staff and IT personnel ensures they have the skills needed to manage digital collections and use new technologies effectively.

In this context, digitization in academic libraries in Davao region plays a pivotal role in enhancing the success and efficiency of library operations. By transforming physical materials into digital formats, academic libraries can offer a range of benefits that improve accessibility, preservation, and resource management. Digitized resources can be accessed from anywhere in the world, breaking down geographical barriers and extending the library's reach to a global audience. Also, users can access digital materials 24/7, providing convenience and flexibility that traditional library hours cannot offer. This is particularly beneficial for remote learners and researchers thereby resulting to higher customer satisfaction and provision of quality services to support the academic needs of the users.

The emerging and clustered themes from this study were thoroughly discussed in the context of lived experiences of academic librarians in digitizing library resources with supporting literature and related studies in the Philippines and other countries. The discussion also explains the reasons behind the emerging themes obtained from the lived experiences of the participants that covers the following, to wit: difficulties of academic librarians in digitizing library resources, strategies of academic librarians to overcome their difficulties in digitizing library resources and forms of support academic librarians need from the administration in order to overcome their difficulties in digitizing library resources.

Difficulties of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources

The digital revolution has transformed information access, and academic libraries are at the forefront of this transformation. However, the journey of digitizing resources is filled with challenges that can impede progress. These encompass technological and infrastructure barriers in digitization, skills and knowledge gaps in digitization, and preservation concerns.

Technological and Infrastructure Barriers in Digitization. Academic librarians face significant challenges in their digitization efforts due to technological and infrastructural barriers. They often experience stress from the lack of high-end equipment, particularly in handling oversized resources that are incompatible with available scanners. Additionally, they struggle to acquire essential equipment and to uphold quality control standards for digitized collections, ensuring their longevity and accessibility, due to insufficient budgets. Inadequate internet connectivity further complicates access to these collections and can limit the reach of digitized resources. Connectivity issues also hinder efficient upload, backup, and sharing of large files, which slow down the entire digitization process and make it challenging to create comprehensive digital collections in a timely manner.

It is proven in the study that academic librarians were challenged on financial limited resources and lack of administrative support which is a hindrance in acquiring high-end specialized software and hardware equipment for digitization efforts that lead to poor quality of digitized resources (Ogunbodede & Onah, 2024). In addition, Boren and Donato (2023); Pandey and Kumar (2020) shared that problematic issues encountered by academic librarians on digitization efforts were financial and technological resources that affect on the digitization progress.

On the other hand, limited internet connectivity, and difficulty in navigating the system interface can hinder the digitization workflow that can slow down processes. At the same time, concerns include accessibility of the digitized collections due to inappropriate domain name, and the need to enhance the digitization features system.

The common concern encountered by academic librarians that hinder in digitalization of resources were problems on internet connectivity or the internet of thing, such as limited wifi facilities, frequent internet connection interruption and user interface for data

processing (Rai et al., 2023). In addition, Gupta and Jagtap (2024) pointed out that the absence of internet connectivity and deficiencies in organizational structures impede operational efficiency on digitization efforts.

The result of the study showed that technological and infrastructure barrier in digitization is one factor that impedes on a successful digitization landscape. Without having enough budget, librarians cannot suffice the digitization equipment in maintain the quality measures of the contents that affect the usability of the resources and meeting the users' demand. Also, internet connectivity issues were challenged in today's digital era, affecting individuals' daily routine because people nowadays, people are dependent on technology. Without internet connection, there is no essence on it.

Skills and Knowledge Gaps in Digitization. Librarians with skills and knowledge gaps in digitization can lead to difficulties in operating equipment, selecting appropriate software, and managing metadata input in the system and cannot sustain efficient and effective performance output. Based on their experiences, the insufficient training opportunities on digitization skills would put valuable collections at risk since scanning process is a tedious process that require specialized skill.

It is proven in the study that the lack of knowledge in digitization efforts challenged the librarians in digitizing library resources. Brink and Packmohr (2023) pointed out that there are difficulties on operating equipment with the technical aspects of digital transformation, like outdated computer systems or complex new software and lack of skills on the operating equipment. Furthermore, there is a need of competencies and skills required by the library personnel in doing digitization efforts to have streamline operations (Awoyemi & Ipadeola, 2024). Also, there is a need for all library personnel to have an in-depth knowledge in utilizing technology and selecting appropriate software. Furthermore, enhanced ICT skills on digitization initiative is needed to secure the longevity of the digital collections (Akintonde & Awujoola, 2024; Borin & Donato, 2023).

In this study, results show that librarians lack the necessary skills for effective digitization processes, hindering the preservation and accessibility of digital information. This deficiency includes a lack of technical expertise, limited knowledge of digital tools and platforms, and insufficient training in managing digital collections.

Preservation Concerns. Digitizing library resources presents a major challenge for academic librarians especially in ensuring the accessibility of the resources. Based on the results of the study, without having data security measures, digitized collections are vulnerable to cyberattacks or hardware failures, potentially leading to data loss.

Furthermore, this study stressed out that the lack of clear preservation policies can result in inconsistent practices since preservation policy is the basic guide in doing digitization efforts. Poor scanning quality due to low-resolution equipment or improper techniques, and incomplete metadata will pose threats to the usability of digitized resources. Converting printed materials into digital format is not an easy job. Girdhar, Coustaty, and Doucet (2023) pointed out that transitioning printed resources into digital landscape is a tedious process were varying lay-outs and metadata inputs were very challenging part of a librarian to secure the validity and accuracy of the contents. In addition, Awoyemi and padeloa (2024); Zhao et al. (2023) stated that academic librarians were challenged in formulating effective strategies on the digital preservation methods like standard policies, poor scanning quality due to inappropriate equipment, and data security where files are prone to data loss and corruption, and the constant need on adaptation of the new trends in technology. Also, academic librarians were challenged on preservation techniques on digitization like incorrect metadata that leads to data losses (Ogunbodede & Onah, 2024).

Indeed, lack of institutional policies and administrative support were factors that impede successful digitization efforts as well as the lack of storage files in sustaining the back-up files of digitized resources (Suita, Eilu & Mutemere, 2024; Borin & Donato, 2023). As the result of this study, challenges highlight the need for comprehensive digitization policies that address data security, regular backups, long-term preservation strategies, scanning standards, and thorough metadata creation.

Strategies of Academic Librarians in Digitizing Library Resources

Academic librarians face numerous difficulties in digitization landscape. Creative approaches or strategies were employed to help librarians overcome these difficulties. These include upgrades the technological infrastructure, training and professional development, and new digital preservation methods.

Upgrade Technological Infrastructure. Upgrading technological infrastructure is an essential factors for successful digitization projects. Acquiring high-quality equipment and software is ideal for digitization projects. Because of budget constraints, academic librarians were often forced to get creative strategies to surpass the difficulties in digital landscape like exploring alternative methods using high-resolution digital cameras instead of scanners. However, this approach requires attention to proper lighting and image capture techniques to ensure sufficient quality. Providing assistance from the administration in developing and adopting digital technologies through staff trainings can help to overcome the difficulties in digitization (Chudaeva, 2023).

Furthermore, the achievement of long-term financial sustainability is paramount to the continued success and expansion of digitization initiative like acquisition of high-quality scanning equipment for sustaining the quality control of the contents, maintainance for physical replacement of the infrastructure and additional manpower for the management of growing digital resources (National Academic Press, 2023; Rily-Ried, 2015).

On the other hand, digitized collections cannot be accessed without the a strong and reliable internet connection to access digitized resources quickly. Additionally, ensuring multiple file backups, preferably on secure cloud storage platforms, safeguards against data loss and guarantees accessibility in case of technical issues. For faster retrieval of information, librarians also employ various search strategies and appropriate metadata inputs.

In today's generation, we are now in the advent of technologies and libraries are increasingly transitioning their physical collections to the digital landscape. Through this, faster retrieval and accessibility of digitized resources were significant factors employed by academic librarians to properly work-out the domain name for the data security, accessibility and usability of the digitized resources (Giulio & Vecchi, 2023). In addition, the unrestricted utilization of the internet can be used in a wide range of areas or fields and it also emphasizes the freedom and flexibility of accessing the digitized resources (Nakano, Jorente & Galindo, 2016).

Indeed, the study shows that there should be prioritization on the investments of technological infrastructure, strengthen quality control mechanisms, and continuous professional development for personnel. Also, faster retrieval and accessibility of digitized resources were significant factors to emphasize the wide range of areas or fields of information where users can have the freedom and flexibility of accessing the digitized collections. In the absence of these critical elements, the effectiveness of collections in fostering engagement will inevitably decline.

Training and Professional Development. Skill development and knowledge sharing are essential strategies for academic librarians to overcome challenges in digitizing library resources. Educating and training staff by attending seminars and workshops even in-house trainings is also important. At the same time, partnering with other libraries or institutions can lead to shared access to equipment and expertise. It is important to keep up by learning new skills on digitization through identifying and developing the required skills and competencies on digitization efforts like proper metadata inputs, and techno-savvy in manipulating the technological infrastructure design for digitized collections (Caganova & Hornakova, 2024). In addition, Banciu (2024) mentioned that full attention in developing librarians' digital skills by attending seminars, workshop, and in-service training is also important for easy access and retrieval of digitized resources.

Furthermore, STPL Global (2024) pointed out that sharing knowledge is a support needed as this is a vital part of human interaction which is essential for personal, organizational, and societal progress. It includes transferring information, experiences, and skills among individuals, teams, and communities. In a fast-changing world, where information is crucial, sharing knowledge is key to stimulating innovation, enhancing problem-solving abilities, and advancing overall development. This study revealed that there is an integration of Transactional Model of Stress and Coping developed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984). In this study, librarians developed practical solutions with mixed emotions on the challenges encountered.

New Digital Preservation Methods. Implementing strategic planning with a focus on policy development, ethical considerations, appropriate preservation methods, and embracing technological advancements, academic librarians ensure a successful digitization project. High-end equipment could greatly improve the viability and quality image of the material (Rinken & Potzschke, 2022). In addition, academic librarians implemented strategic planning and policies for continuous development of the digitalization of resources since strategic planning was the basic guide in securing digitized collections (Dadzie & Walt, 2015).

The institution would also help in providing a reference on policy making in the use of digital landscape to secure the data privacy and to have smooth flow of operations (Yu & Liu, 2024). In addition, digitizing library resources has a major challenge but the most helpful strategy in overcoming the difficulties is to incorporate long-term planning and the appropriate preservation methods with the inclusion of ethical consideration as this has major contributions to surpass on digitization challenges and to secure the sustainability of the digitized collections (Bakhshi, 2016). Furthermore, digital preservation system is composed of policies, approaches and actions like handling techniques with the aim of keeping the digital objects authentic and accessible to users for a long period of time (Sinha, Kumar & Singh, 2022).

Moreover, results in this study show that there is an incorporation of Digital Curation Lifecycle Model by Higgins (2018). This is shown in the strategies employed by the participants such as strategized plan of action, developed preservation methodologies from acquisition process to quality assurance for security, accessibility, and usability of digitized resources.

Forms of Support Needed by Academic Librarians from the Administration

Academic librarians have identified and shared the different forms of support that they need from the administration to realize their digitization projects. These forms of support include financial resource allocation, administrative support for policy development, and expanding collaboration for resource sharing of digitized collections.

Increase Financial Resource Allocation. Academic librarians require vigorous support from the administration to address challenges in digitizing library resources, especially concerning adequate financial resource allocation. To overcome these difficulties effectively, academic librarians need the following forms of support from the administration in staff development, financial support for training, benchmarking funds, and sufficient funds for technological infrastructure and other operation cost for digitization initiatives.

In today's era, digitization is essential to foster lifelong learning, and for the users to access vast amount of information. To optimize its effectiveness, the administration should support in sustaining digitization efforts particularly in giving sufficient budget. Through

enough budget, all plan on digitization will be realized.

Administrative Support for Policy Development. Academic librarians require strong administrative support in developing and implementing effective policies by crafting clear guidelines, enhancing new policies to reflect the institution's commitment for innovation, and technical support for data security and privacy of the digitized resources.

Administrative support for policy development is significant to have successful digitization efforts. First, it ensures that policies are aligned with the organization's goals, as administrators provide insight into the strategic direction of the institution. Secondly, administrative support lends credibility to policies, that guide and lead the staff and personnel on the proper procedure on digitization initiatives. Additionally, administrators can allocate resources and provide guidance to facilitate the implementation of policies effectively. Their support also helps in navigating any challenges or conflicts that may arise during the policy development process, ultimately leading to the successful implementation of policies.

Thus, librarians need support from the administration to incorporate long-term strategic plans and policies on digitization efforts to secure the usability and accessibility of the resources with the application of the ethical consideration (Udem, Ejikeme, & Benjamin, 2015).

Expanding Collaboration for Resource Sharing of Digitized Collections. Academic librarians can overcome digitization challenges by fostering collaboration and resource sharing with the administration's support, through Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)/Agreement, consortium activities, and collaboration with digitization specialists. Hall (2024) stressed out the significance of collaboration can create a stronger sense of community. Experts will ensure the benefits to improve the core aspects of teaching and research to users. In addition, Leclercq and Rijshouwer (2022) stated that community engagement and knowledge collaboration among expertise have great contribution for raising awareness on digitization effort.

Furthermore, fostering internal collaboration through enhanced network connectivity, knowledge peer exchange, and strategic external partnerships can significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of digitization initiatives (Witschel et al., 2019). Through it, academic librarians, in collaboration of the administrator, will place policy making guidelines and come up with the Memorandum of Understanding or Memorandum of Agreement with other institutions on the use of digital resources and resource sharing initiatives to have smooth flow connections between both parties.

The exchange of information using digital library collections has become an appealing and viable idea for library and information globally. The support from the administration is an essential factor to realize an efficient and effective digitization initiatives, since resource sharing or consortia was a great practice in different institutions. With this, users can widely utilize the available resources in different institutions (Singh, 2018). As the result, there should be a greater focus in providing the required forms of support academic librarians need from the administration on professional commitment to enhance their efforts in digitizing printed materials (Ikonne, Unegbu, & Sulaiman, 2024).

Conclusions

Digitizing library resources is of paramount importance in modernizing libraries and enhancing access to information. By converting print materials into digital formats, libraries can significantly improve accessibility, allowing users to retrieve and interact with resources remotely and conveniently. Digitization also ensures the preservation of valuable collections, protecting them from physical deterioration and enabling long-term access for future generations. Moreover, digital resources facilitate efficient search and retrieval processes, saving time for users and enhancing research capabilities. Embracing digitization enables libraries to save space and costs associated with physical storage, while also fostering collaboration, sharing, and innovation in the digital realm.

This study provides insight into how academic librarians overcome challenges in digitization through creative approaches and by identifying essential support needed from administrations and organizations. It sheds light on significant obstacles faced by academic librarians in their efforts to digitize library resources, including technological and infrastructure limitations, skills and knowledge gaps, and preservation concerns. A major challenge lies in the unavailability of suitable equipment for digitizing large-scale resources that standard scanners cannot handle. Additionally, librarians struggle with a lack of software enhancements needed to maintain high-quality standards in digitized resources, limiting effective quality control.

Budget constraints are another critical barrier, as inadequate funding can hinder the success of digitization initiatives, including acquiring essential technology for preservation and securing long-term financial support for ongoing updates and maintenance. Without sufficient resources, and strong internet connection, efforts to build a sustainable digital landscape risk being ineffective, as budget allocations are essential for achieving desired outcomes in digital preservation and ensuring the accessibility and usability of digitized collections.

In addition, skills and knowledge gaps, alongside preservation concerns, present considerable challenges in the digitization of library resources, where librarians face limitations in digitization techniques, advanced software, and digital preservation practices, which can compromise the quality and longevity of digital collections. These skill gaps do not only affect the accuracy and accessibility of digitized materials but they also impede effective quality control and long-term maintenance of digital landscape that are vulnerable

to technological obsolescence and data degradation.

However, the study also offers a beacon of hope. By implementing well-defined strategies, librarians can effectively navigate these difficulties. Upgrading technological infrastructure like acquisition of specialized hardware and software applications, improving internet connection, exploring creative funding avenues, and investing in staff development empower librarians to embark on successful digitization journeys. Additionally, adopting appropriate technologies, crafting and implementing digital preservation methods and policies strategically will maintain the longevity and accessibility of the digitized collections for future generation use.

In addition to the strategies employed by academic librarians to ensure the longevity of digital collections, support from the administration is also a crucial factor. Administrative support is essential for implementing effective strategies in digitizing library resources, including approaches such as knowledge-sharing initiatives, collaboration with external partners, and sustainable practices. These forms of support help optimize resources, improve efficiency, and ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of digital collections. Adequate resource allocation, policy development, training opportunities, collaborative efforts, and strategic planning from the administration empower librarians to successfully navigate the complexities of digitization projects and achieve meaningful results.

Indeed, addressing the difficulties, implementing strategic approaches, and receiving necessary support from the administration are key factors in enhancing the digitization of library resources in academic settings. By recognizing these challenges, implementing effective strategies, and fostering a supportive environment, academic librarians can successfully digitize library resources to meet the evolving needs of users and ensure the preservation and accessibility of valuable information for future generations.

References

- Adarkwah, M.A., Okagbue, E. F., Oladipo, O.A., Mekonen, Y. K., Anulika, A. G., Nchekwubemchukwu, I. S., Okafor, M. U., Chineta, O. M., Muhideen, S., & Islam, A.A. (2024). Exploring the transformative journey of academic libraries in Africa before and after covid-19 and in the generative ai era. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102900>
- Ahmed, S. K. (2024). The pillars of trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health*, 2, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2024.100051>
- Applied Doctoral Center. (2023). Trustworthiness of the data. <https://resources.nu.edu/c.php?g=1013606&p=8394398>
- Ashikuzzaman, M. D. (2023). Digitization of library resources: benefits and challenges. LIS education Network. <https://www.lisedunetwork.com/digitization-and-library/>
- Azim, N. A.M., Yatin, S. F. M., Jensonray, R.C.A., & Ayub, S. (2018). digitization of records and archives: issues and concerns. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8 (9), 170–178. DOI: 10.6007/IJARBS/v8-i9/4582
- Bhandari, P. (2021). Ethical considerations in research: Types & examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-ethics/>
- Colaizzi P. F. (1978) Psychological research as the phenomenologist views it. In: *Existential Phenomenological Alternatives for Psychology* (eds R. Valle & M. King). Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Consultative Community for Space Data System. (2002). Reference model for an open archival information system (OAIS): Recommendation for space data system standards. <https://siarchives.si.edu/sites/default/files/pdfs/650x0b1.PDF>
- Correia, S., & Luck, S. (2024). Digitizing historical balance sheet data: A practitioner's guide. *Explorations in Economic History*, 87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2022.101475>
- Dela Cruz, T.S. (2018). A feasibility study on integrating the Philippine government documents collection of the University of the Philippines National College of public administration and the governance library to the digital archives at UP Diliman. Undergraduate thesis. University library, UP Diliman <https://digitalarchives.upd.edu.ph/item/25871/12/Ec2hDki0Ck9b22FGFiEC9KK1>
- Elridge, S. (2024). Data analysis. <https://www.britannica.com/science/data-analysis>
- Farnsworth Group. (2023). How to achieve trustworthiness in qualitative research. <https://www.thefarnsworthgroup.com/blog/trustworthiness-qualitative-research>
- Gomez, M. R. S., Valdez, M. G., & Almodovar, M.A.P. (2023). Data Protection & Privacy: Taking Action in Data Protection. <https://www.pwc.com/ph/en/risk-assurance/risk-assurance-it/data-protection-privacy-ra-it.html>
- Gupta, S., Jagtap, S. (2024). Unlocking digital growth: Overcoming barriers to digital transformation for Indian food SMEs. *Discov Food* 4, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44187-024-00131-6>
- Hassan, M. (2024). Ethical considerations: Types, examples and writing guide. <https://researchmethod.net/ethical-considerations/>
- Higgins, S. (2008). The DCC Curation Lifecycle Model. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 3(1), 134-140. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v3i1.48>

- Ho, L., & Limpacher, A. (2022). What is phenomenological research design: Essential guide to coding qualitative data. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>
- Hotjar. (2023). 5 qualitative data analysis methods: What is qualitative data analysis? <https://www.hotjar.com/qualitative-data-analysis/methods/>
- Indah, R. N., Geddy, A. S. N. B., Rusli, F.A., & Syam, R. Z.A. (2024). Digitization of gray literature in the library of the national research and innovation agency. *KnE Social Sciences*. DOI:10.18502/kss.v9i12.15883
- Ingle, V. D. (2022). Digitalization of libraries: Issues & challenges. <https://ijfans.org/uploads/paper/0515936bc6d942f44bafd2051e71499f.pdf>
- Kaur, H. (2015). Digital preservation of manuscripts: An Indian perspective with special reference to Punjab. *International Symposium on Emerging Trends and Technologies in Libraries and Information Services*, 271-274. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/7048210>
- Kipaan, L. P. (n.d.). Digitization Best Practices in a Financially Challenged University Library: The BSU Experience. http://rizal.lib.admu.edu.ph/2012conf/fullpaper/FINAL%20Full%20paper_Kipaan.pdf
- Lacuata, A. N. (2020). Digitization of library resources in higher education institutions in La Union, Philippines. *Preservation, Digital Technology & Culture*, 49(4), 139-158. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pdte-2020-0031>
- Lagas, S., & Isip, J. (2023). Challenges to Digital Services in Philippine Academic Libraries. *Philippine Journal of Librarianship and Information Studies*, 43(1), 27-38. <https://phjlis.org/index.php/phjlis/article/view/133>
- Lefuma, S. (2017). Access to and use of electronic information resources in the academic libraries of the Lesotho Library Consortium. <http://repository.tml.nul.ls/handle/20.500.14155/1320>
- Lincoln, Y.S., & Guba, E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.
- McGinty (2024). Developing a digital library: Scale requires partnership. <https://www.ala.org/acrl/publications/whitepapers/nashville/mcginty>
- Methodologist. (2023). Informed consent: Empowering research participants with knowledge and choice. <https://methodologists.net/The-Ethics-of-Consent-Ensuring-Participants-are-Fully-Informed>
- Nafisah, S. (2022). Urgency of digitizing school libraries in Indonesia's post-truth era: A cross-perspective review. *Jurnal Kajian Informasi & Perpustakaan* 10(2), 157-172. DOI:10.24198/jkip.v10i2.35702
- National Privacy Commission (2023). Privacy Statement. <https://privacy.gov.ph/npc-privacy-policy-2/>
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2023). What Is Convenience Sampling? Definition & Examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/convenience-sampling/>
- Nneji (2018). Digitization of academic library resources: A case study of Donal E. U. Ekong Library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1990>
- Owen, T. (2023). Library of congress digitization strategy: 2023-2027. <https://blogs.loc.gov/thesignal/2023/02/library-of-congress-digitization-strategy-2023-2027/>
- Pandey, P. & Misra, R. (2014) Digitization of library materials in academic libraries: issues and challenges. *Journal of Industrial and Intelligent Information*, Vol. 2 (2), pp. 136-141.
- Polit, D.F., & Beck, C.T. (2014). *Essentials of nursing research: Appraising evidence for nursing practice* (8th ed.). Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Rungcharoensuksri, S. (2016). Guideline for digital curation for the Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn anthropology centre's digital repository: Preliminary outcome. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 203-211. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-49304-6_24#citeas
- Shenton, A. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. <http://www.crec.co.uk/docs/Trustworthyaper.pdf>
- Schwartz, M. (2020). Preserving the future of public media. *public media stack*. <https://publicmediastack.com/workflow-stage/storage-archiving-essay/>
- Soni, D.N. (2023). Digital transformation of libraries: Challenges and strategies in information and library science. *International Journal of Research in Humanities & Soc. Sciences*, 11, (2). https://www.rajmr.com/ijrhs/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/IJRHS_2023_vol11_issue_02_10.pdf

- Tenny, S., Brannan, J. M., & Brannan, G. D. (2022). Qualitative study. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470395/#:~:text=Qualitative%20research%20uses%20several%20techniques,that%20>
- Tobin, D. (2023). What is data privacy—and why is it important. [https://www.integrate.io/blog/what-is-data-privacy-why-is-it-important/#:~:text=Preserving Individual Autonomy: Data privacy,exploited or misused without consent.](https://www.integrate.io/blog/what-is-data-privacy-why-is-it-important/#:~:text=Preserving%20Individual%20Autonomy%3A%20Data%20privacy,exploited%20or%20misused%20without%20consent.)
- Trochim, W. M. K. (2023). Qualitative validity. <https://conjointly.com/kb/qualitative-validity/>
- Udem, O. K., Ejikeme, O. I., & Benjamin, O. (2015). Digitization of library resources in university libraries: A Practical approach, challenges and prospects. <http://repository.unizik.edu.ng/handle/123456789/724>
- Ugwu, C. N., & Val, E. (2023). Qualitative research. Researchgate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367221023_Qualitative_Research
- Uy, D. (2023). What the Future Holds for Public Libraries in the Philippines. News narrative. <https://newsnarratives.com/2023/08/07/public-libraries-in-the-philippines/>
- Yaya, J.A., & Adeeko, K. (2024). Digitization of educational resources in Nigerian academic libraries: Prospects, challenges and the way forward. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, 3 (1), 1594-1600. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382596806_DIGITIZATION_OF_EDUCATIONAL_RESOURCES_IN_NIGERIAN_ACADEMIC_LIBRARIES_PROSPECTS_CHALLENGES_AND_THE_WAY_FORWARD

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ruth R. Armilla, RL, MLIS

Cor Jesu College, Inc. – Philippines

Maria Lorena M. Abangan, PhD

Cor Jesu College, Inc. – Philippines